

Addendum 2: Megafauna Extinction Events

Update to the Thunderbolt Extinction Model; the Surprising truth of the Younger Dryas Event that Changes Everything

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Recommended Viewing for animated gifs at: <https://bit.ly/3jFc0pr>

ABSTRACT

The death of our previous star Shamash (or Zurvan, Anu, Ra, Kronos, or El) is probably due to the approach of our solar system towards the star Sol (or Apollo), was a disastrous, spectacular flaring event that lasted 2k-3k years 12kya-9kya. The event ended the Atlantean Period and precipitated the Tepe Period. It was, however, incredibly catastrophic for the reasons covered in the paper. This included “high carp floods,” deluges, super winds (Tai Feng), thunderbolt arc-blasts, mountain and valley formations and carving, and impactor/errata. In the original paper, the moon and its clear signs of electrical arc discharge excavation (see M Plates in Appendices) was our ideal source of the energy for the YD events. However, the Cosmic Egg research starting with the Ramesses Stele and continued at Maputo and Bakoni, Gobekli Tepe, etc. (over three dozen sites), led to a revisiting of the concept of “who was the Lord of Diadems?” After reviewing “Enki and the World Order,” it became clear that the event was far more complex than any in the mainstream or altstream had anticipated, which readily explains the complexities of the Solar System with its otherwise inexplicable arrangements, orbits, angles, and compositions. The outcome is that the previously proposed Extended Timeline is upheld and shows rough correspondence, sometimes precise (such as 7kya Jovian boundary), with the catastrophic cycles. The periods, from Tepe, Archaic, Megalithic, and Transition seem to correspond very well with solar system re-arrangement and breakdown according to myth, rock art, mound building phases, megalith building, and other mythic records. It is clear, therefore the moon (Watcher) was only a middle part during the Jovian transition, while the actual source of energetics for the YD event is probably the flaring death of Shamash/Anu. Moreover, a new mechanism for other ice ages is proposed.

Keywords: Shamash - Ice Ages - Younger Dryas - Impacts - Thunderbolts - Megafauna

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Part 1 - Cosmic Eggs in One Basket

It's no secret that we exist on one planet, and this is a precarious position to be in¹. This does not appear to have bothered mankind in biologically modern form for 200 thousand years², until roughly 40kya³. At that time the skies were purple, the seasons only wet and dry, and there was not much to mankind⁴. At the beginning of our rock art we started with beautiful representations of animal life and the great harmony of nature⁵. Somewhere roughly 16kya-12kya this began to morph⁶. It was in these early early days, called the Atlantean Period⁷, which we can ascribe as a time of peaceful transition. Something this way comes, and the star above us took on a particularly striking prominence⁸. Something made it glow, and a revolving boat began to form upon it⁹. Moreover, it began to stretch from an equatorial:polar diameter ratio (DR) of 1 out to 1.23 at the time of the Ramesses Stele¹⁰. This change was accompanied, apparently, by an excess of green, and a change in the atmosphere. The sky "fell" (the plasma sheath ceased) revealing the Heavens and the "waters were separated from the waters"¹¹ [that they reflected upon]. To this day black is the color of the water phase in China¹². Plants had to adapt quickly, but nevertheless to this day prefer purple and UV rays¹³ despite an abundance of green spectra from the sun.

Figure 1 - Solar Spectra; credit: brilliant.org

¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Global_catastrophic_risk

²

<https://flexbooks.ck12.org/cbook/ck-12-college-human-biology-flexbook-2.0/section/7.7/primary/lesson/evolution-of-modern-humans-chumbio#:~:text=Modern%20Humans%20in%20Prehistory,much%20of%20the%20Old%20World.>

³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Behavioral_modernity

⁴ <https://www.ancient-origins.net/ancient-places-africa/36400-bc-historical-time-zep-tepi-theory-002617>

⁵ <https://www.ancienthistorylists.com/pre-history/top-10-oldest-art-ever-discovered/>

⁶ <https://www.newscientist.com/article/dn1590-animal-headed-humans-appear-in-earliest-art/>

⁷ https://www.academia.edu/36753645/On_the_Origins_of_Religions pp. 1-3

⁸ <https://www.scribd.com/doc/203731554/The-Saturn-Myth-David-N-Talbot-1980>

⁹ *ibid.*

¹⁰ https://www.academia.edu/38492475/The_Solar_Orb_in_Egypt

¹¹ Genesis 1:6

¹² <https://musculoskeletalkey.com/the-water-phase-the-kidneys-and-bladder/>

¹³ <https://www.lumigrowth.com/light-essential/>

So what was it that precipitated this change? Why was it so profound? What is contained in the earliest texts such as the “Enuma Elish”¹⁴ and especially “Enki and the World Order”¹⁵ that teaches us a whole different cosmology and cosmogony¹⁶?

In short: our “Creator God” died¹⁷... birthing as a father-mother 3 other sons... and was reborn as the planet Saturn (Enki). From there we were “hot potatoed” around a three-body system which was increasingly chaotic and erratic. Being dragged behind our parent, we had numerous strange conjunctions and the “gods” wandered about, having, what appeared to humanity to be, wars, adventures, and playing in the “intestines”¹⁸ of the dead god. Later the concept of a central High Lord¹⁹ was enacted, and the lordship was passed about, mostly father to son, excepting Poseidon/Shiva’s role²⁰. Eventually the hereditary Lordship was decided to have begun with Jupiter/Jove/Jehovah (Uchell or Shang Di or Odin or Marduk/Enlil), which then begat hero sons/demi-gods, which then begat messiahs and mankind, etc. The most famous of the heroes were the planet Mars, Mercury, the goddess Venus, the moon which people worshiped and fell into Sin²¹, and Jupiter itself. It isn’t clear why the sun was only worshiped in the Transition Period to now, except that it was inconsequentially small (from our perspective) *until* it ripped us from our chaotic orbit around Jupiter and put us into magnetic phased locking²² where our 4 orbits remain to this day (Mercury through Mars). Venus, having been ripped out of the heart of Saturn²³, probably had a clash not only with Mars but Jupiter, as Zeus is said to have sent Athena away from the din of battle towards the sun²⁴, where already Hermes-Mercury /Thoth/Heimdallr had gone to get enlightenment and guard the Rainbow Bridge. But the interaction of Mars and Earth+Moon remained a bit longer, til even the Romans and Chinese had a tradition of the “deaths of 9 of the 10 gods”^{25 26 27}

Still, the elapse of time from the beginning of the Tepe Period²⁸ through the Deluge²⁹, the planet flipping over, and the arrival of the moon and all the main events was so long that no culture could contain the whole story... except perhaps India which had 2 (or 3) seriously long epics to record it. In Columbia, natives painted 8 **miles** of rock wall with depictions of the events³⁰, including the destruction of megafauna³¹ and the Clash of the

¹⁴ <https://www.sacred-texts.com/ane/enuma.htm>

¹⁵ <https://etcsl.orinst.ox.ac.uk/section1/tr113.htm>

¹⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=p5cWZeQrQ7Q>

¹⁷ This is not a religious statement, and the author has his own faith that God Lives. It’s a statement about events and interpretations of the people of that time.

https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1QnRXGf1kju3C_CZX06njKK-tnrbGGjq5kOGkRAI-zSM/edit?usp=sharing

¹⁸ <https://thepostgradchronicles.org/2017/09/30/blood-eagles-fatal-walks-and-hung-meat-assessing-viking-torture/>

Compare with lines 192-209 of “Enki and the World Order” (slide 10) “trailing glory, bestowing powers on the people from sunrise to sunset: your powers are superior powers, untouchable, and your heart is complex and inscrutable”

¹⁹ https://www.academia.edu/387444706/Uchell_the_High_Lord_and_Shang_Di

²⁰ Whilst it is clear that Saturn ejected Neptune based on the evidence, and that Poseidon is Kronos’ child, this doesn’t fit the desired narrative, so Zeus is the “first born” and Hera second born daughter (as Saturn with rings), while Neptune is relegated to third place.

²¹ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sin_\(mythology\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sin_(mythology))

²² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=V5FyFvgxUhE>

²³ [Readings in Classical Nahuatl: The Death of Quetzalcoatl](#)

²⁴ https://home.ubalt.edu/ntygfit/ai_01_pursuing_fame/ai_01_tell/iliad05.htm

²⁵ <https://mythopedia.com/chinese-mythology/gods/hou-yi/>

²⁶ <https://www.jstor.org/stable/627003>

²⁷ <https://www.tertullian.org/rpearse/mithras/display.php?page=main>

²⁸ 12kya - 9kya

²⁹ 6kya?

³⁰

<https://hyperallergic.com/605541/archaeologists-discover-eight-miles-of-prehistoric-rock-art-the-sistine-chapel-of-the-ancients/>

³¹

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332686916_Plasma_Petroglyphs_Plasmaglyphs_Petroglyphs_Earthworks_and_the_Megafauna_Extinction

Titans. No other explanation for such assiduous effort has ever been given. In the Ohio River Valley, a mysterious Allegewi people recorded the north pole vortices of Jupiter to within a ridiculous lack of coincidence, 4×10^{-45} chance³². That's statistically a 0% chance no matter how you look at it. This proved they had math, writing, and line of site from our northern hemisphere to Jupiter's north pole; more on this later. But the southern pole's pentacle arrangement was also important worldwide.

Figure 2 - Jupiter's Poles; Credit: Caltech

All of this we find because of the strange recordings of the Cosmic Eggs, worldwide, on every habitable continent. It is a story of an interpreted stellar flare event where plasma was ejected into space, and gasses congealed under stressful electrical conditions, and formed three gas giants: Saturn, Jupiter, and Neptune. Later they were joined (or another unspecified ejection was made) by the planet Uranus, misnamed obviously since the original purple sky was Ooranus itself³³.

What should be done with this knowledge? In this part we will do a systematic breakdown of the evidence of the Cosmic Eggs, without which a broader picture of the YD and subsequent events is impossible to prove or understand. But the analysis of which gives context and bearing to the identity and behavior of the gods, the myths they inhabit, and the reasons for many of our profound mysteries in religion, science, and cosmology which remain scientifically unexplained til this day, and many of which have only supernatural explanations. This paper is not intended to discomfort the religious or spiritual, but edify and enlighten them. The Messiah phenomenon has an origin³⁴, but beyond that, is not in the scope of this paper to address its reality of form and function³⁵.

³²

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332316290_Hopewellian_Octagons_Proof_that_the_Allegewi_Astronomers_could_see_Jupiter_up_close_Analysis_of_the_Octagon_formation_of_Chillicothe_and_Newark_Earthworks

³³ Therefore the planet will be called Uranus, while the original plasma sheath around Shamash will be called Ooranus, as it was the purple sky god.

³⁴ <https://opensiuc.lib.siu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2226&context=ocj>

³⁵ Nor would the author propose to impose his faith upon the reader.

Maputo, Bakoni, Gobekli Tepe, and Peru

In a previous paper³⁶, the author has described the antiquity and meaning of these two sites, and the “secrets” held there about the star’s breakdown³⁷. Indeed, comparisons to other sites at Sardinia et al. are made to reveal the details of the events.

The arrival of Sol and the concentric rings surrounding it is mirrored from Kentucky to Peru, but the true depth of profundity of that archetype remains to be explored in a future paper. By and large, the paper was about the cosmic egg. So what happened between the 1.23 DR and the warping and stretching to 1.4, 1.5, 1.75, and even 2.0! found at other sites? Why did the Cosmic Egg begin to have a “flat butt”, “flat bottom”, “hatching” upper left, and eventually the double-lobed “legs” or “beak” from the bottom right? At this time the author’s only explanations are:

1. Sol’s gravity
2. LMH Ejection³⁸
3. Combination of the two and EM forces.

It may be that there is a plasma function, some EMF caused force, or other flaring impetus, but it is not known, because all writings are from the Transition and Religious Period, and not from the Tepe or Archaic Period³⁹. When they are proposed to have come down from the Megalithic, strangely they are missing the details we do know about. Instead the shapes of the star are replaced with archetypal monsters, therianthropes, demons, and other deformities, which have now been anthropomorphized and artistically and religiously altered, to suit thousands of years of culture. But when we see the original carvings at Gobekli Tepe, they went from Vulture to Pig to Lion (flare?) to Lizard or Crocodile, etc. The belly “drooped” from flat to larger and large as the star came apart, but the key is that no matter the head of the animal, the legs to the lower right, which are themselves repeated as the entire Enclosure D, as an entryway into the sacred “circle”, are still double lobed, and bent.

Figure 3 - Double lobe “legs” and plasma sheath around solar center (Enclosure D)

³⁶ https://www.academia.edu/42656690/Secret_Held_in_Maputo

³⁷ <https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1BwWDV9VIYx1piNulkeNooly-ix4mWTWg1g0z0HUxmPs/edit?usp=sharing>

³⁸ <http://www.ptep-online.com/2013/PP-33-14.PDF>

³⁹ This important chronological point has been glossed over by the mainstream and alstream alike.

Figure 4 - Göbekli Tepe

In Peru, meanwhile, a “new” “Nazca” line has emerged, which is in the form of a meme-like “cat”.

Figure 5: Oldest Geoglyph in Peru;
credit: The Week⁴⁰

Of course it has nothing to do with the Internet, or meme culture, and so what is shown is instead first the death of the star, the birth of Neptune, and a subsequent plasma sheath around the special relationship shared by Jupiter and Saturn after the initial split. There was a large energy component which made the relationship of the two brothers, typified by Enki and Enlil, or Rama and Lakshmana, special. But the third body

⁴⁰ <https://www.theweek.in/news/world/2020/10/24/oldest-geoglyph-discovered-in-peru.html>

shown forming in the “south” of the “Nazca Meme Cat” is obviously of note⁴¹, because it would have been this event which marked the end of a peaceful era, and the beginning of trouble. It was this event which almost certainly ended the Tepe Period, and mankind’s ease of life above ground, and sent him down below. The Ramayana makes clear this one eyed **blue** monster⁴² was eventually tamed into a god, which appears to have briefly ruled mankind. But the simple fact was that a three body system was a recipe for *more doom*.

Nevertheless, what these sites teach us is the importance of a phased analysis of the Cosmic Egg, and the breakdown, not only for record and chronology, but simple cultural significance. It might, in time lead us to understand the differentiation in religion, war, language (or writing more specifically), and of course diffusion of mankind.

Figure 6: Kabandha (Cyclops, child of Poseidon/Neptune) from the Ramayana⁴³

⁴¹ Also notice the similarities of the “stomach” of the cat... to Gobekli Tepe enclosure D. The flat butt, flat bottom, and hatching on the same upper left side, as well as a stretching. We see a progression of the event from left to right. It’s a very clear picture of the creation of the three body problem.

⁴² <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kabandha>

⁴³ Note the Kabandha had no head. Just a body and “mask” like mouth and arms and legs. It reaches out to grasp the two fairer gods. Obviously at this time we were closer to Neptune, hence the thunderbolts of Shiva and Poseidon, and it would have appeared to dwarf the other two gods. Later the Kabandha is transformed into a fair blue skinned god.

Phase Data

Table 1 - Site data (pt 1) of Diameter Ratio measurements⁴⁴

Site	X	Y	X:Y	alt X	alt Y	alt X:Y	avg X:Y
Ramesses Stele A	0.4852	0.393	1.234605598				1.234605598
RS B	0.1642	0.15	1.094666667				1.094666667
RS C1	0.259	0.245	1.057142857				1.057142857
RS C2	0.2475	0.224	1.104910714				1.104910714
RS D	0.146	0.1262	1.156893819				1.156893819
RS E	0.1388	0.1319	1.052312358				1.052312358
RS F	0.119	0.0922	1.290672451				1.290672451
Ramses II	0.799	0.694	1.15129683				1.15129683
Chia Stele	0.861	0.692	1.244219653				1.244219653
Maputo (big)	6.75	5.75	1.173913043				1.173913043
Maputo (small)	5.75	4.6	1.25				1.25
Maputo (B3)	3.7	3.4	1.088235294				1.088235294
Maputo (hatching)	11.5	10.1	1.138613861	10.7	10.1	1.059405941	1.099009901
<i>Maputo (chick)</i>	5.1	5.1	1				1
Bakoni	12.25	11	1.113636364				1.113636364
Vulture Stone (egg)	0.604	0.529	1.141776938				1.141776938
<i>Gobekli Tepe A</i>	4.7	3.1	1.516129032				1.516129032
<i>GT B</i>	3.7	3.1	1.193548387				1.193548387
<i>GT C</i>	5.2	4.1	1.268292683	4.3	3.3	1.303030303	1.285661493
<i>GT D</i>	6.9	4.5	1.533333333	5.5	4.1	1.341463415	1.437398374
VS (chick)	0.328	0.2841	1.154523055				1.154523055
VS (main)	0.8812	0.7658	1.150692087				1.150692087
Culvertown, KY	0.3511	0.237	1.481434599				1.481434599
Lexington Earthwork	12.7	7.1	1.788732394				1.788732394
Lexington (Chick)	1	1	1				1
Maputo Flower 2	6.5	4.8	1.354166667				1.354166667
Maputo Duo A	10.6	9	1.177777778				1.177777778
MD B	2.75	2.25	1.222222222				1.222222222
MD C	3.95	3	1.316666667				1.316666667

⁴⁴ <http://bit.ly/2UJw95>

Wondjina, Tasmania A	0.682	0.491	1.389002037			1.389002037
WT B	0.42	0.3151	1.332910187			1.332910187
WT C (chick)	0.191	0.1381	1.383055757			1.383055757
WT D	0.73	0.5452	1.33895818			1.33895818
WT E	0.155	0.1095	1.415525114			1.415525114
WT F	0.19	0.129	1.472868217			1.472868217
WT G	1.045	0.777	1.344916345			1.344916345
WT H	0.356	0.3519	1.011651037			1.011651037
WT I	0.331	0.2673	1.238309016			1.238309016
WT J	0.2156	0.19	1.134736842			1.134736842
WT K	0.264	0.2009	1.31408661			1.31408661
WT L	0.7405	0.258	2.870155039			2.870155039
Vernal Spiral A	0.443	0.4132	1.072120039			1.072120039
VS B	0.4181	0.3731	1.120611096			1.120611096
VS C	0.199	0.1762	1.129398411			1.129398411
VS D	0.095	0.0833	1.140456182			1.140456182
Vernal European Cup A	1.0398	0.9789	1.062212688			1.062212688
VEC B	1.004	0.9671	1.03815531			1.03815531
VEC C1	0.442	0.3958	1.116725619			1.116725619
VEC C2	0.429	0.3822	1.12244898			1.12244898
VEC C3	0.488	0.4161	1.172795001			1.172795001
VEC D	0.8081	0.795	1.016477987			1.016477987
VEC E	0.847	0.847	1			1
VEC F	0.314	0.2391	1.313258051			1.313258051
Vernal Area, UT A1	0.253	0.2048	1.235351563			1.235351563
VAUT A2	0.442	0.364	1.214285714			1.214285714
VAUT A3	0.667	0.565	1.180530973			1.180530973
VAUT B1	0.136	0.111	1.225225225			1.225225225
VAUT B2	0.2971	0.2581	1.151104223			1.151104223
VAUT C	0.2152	0.1225	1.756734694			1.756734694
VAUT D	0.2049	0.1731	1.183708839			1.183708839
VAUT E	0.9249	0.8405	1.100416419			1.100416419
VAUT F	0.4001	0.2619	1.527682321			1.527682321
VAUT G	2.05	1.8	1.138888889			1.138888889
VAUT H	3.2	2.85	1.122807018			1.122807018
VAUT I	3.25	3.1	1.048387097			1.048387097

VAUT J	1.4	1.25	1.12			1.12
VAUT K	0.8	0.65	1.230769231			1.230769231
Three Kings Panel A	0.603	0.455	1.325274725			1.325274725
TKP B	0.372	0.32	1.1625			1.1625
TKP C	0.27	0.222	1.216216216			1.216216216
TKP D	0.2393	0.2085	1.147721823			1.147721823
TKP E	0.2572	0.1511	1.702183984			1.702183984
TKP Z (chick)	0.4015	0.3385	1.186115214			1.186115214
Uluu Kata Tjuta	6.4	3.7	1.72972973			1.72972973
Uluru A	1.3	0.9	1.444444444			1.444444444
Uluru B	2.2	1.7	1.294117647			1.294117647
Uluru C	1.7	1.3	1.307692308			1.307692308
Uluru D	1.8	1.6	1.125			1.125
Three Rivers, NM	0.3524	0.3079	1.144527444			1.144527444
Tasmania (large) A	2.9	2.3	1.260869565			1.260869565
Taz B	3.5	2.9	1.206896552			1.206896552
Taz C	2	1.7	1.176470588			1.176470588
Taz D	1.9	1.6	1.1875			1.1875
Taz E	2.75	2.15	1.279069767			1.279069767
Taz F	2.3	1.75	1.314285714			1.314285714
Taz G	1.45	1	1.45			1.45
S America A1	0.1651	0.126	1.31031746			1.31031746
SA A2	0.4335	0.3015	1.437810945			1.437810945
SA B	0.237	0.202	1.173267327			1.173267327
SA C	0.2082	0.175	1.189714286			1.189714286
SA D	0.572	0.571	1.001751313			1.001751313
SA F	0.32	0.1925	1.662337662			1.662337662
Haida Copper A	0.324	0.312	1.038461538			1.038461538
HC B	0.2416	0.2119	1.140160453			1.140160453
Pennsylvania	0.3805	0.2809	1.354574582			1.354574582
Onake Kindi, India A	0.758	0.5835	1.299057412			1.299057412
OKI B	0.715	0.6452	1.108183509			1.108183509
OKI C	0.6656	0.5957	1.117340943			1.117340943
OKI D	0.6435	0.6375	1.009411765			1.009411765
OKI E	0.6547	0.606	1.080363036			1.080363036
OKI F	0.6355	0.5439	1.168413311			1.168413311

OKI G	0.7405	0.5285	1.401135289			1.401135289
OKI H	9.8	8.85	1.107344633			1.107344633
OKI I	0.459	0.4259	1.077717774			1.077717774
OKI J (chick)	2.4	2.2	1.090909091			1.090909091
OKI K	8.8	8.8	1			1
OKI L	0.5665	0.3835	1.477183833			1.477183833
Kern Co A	4.3	4.2	1.023809524			1.023809524
KC B1	3.2	2.65	1.20754717			1.20754717
KC B2	6.8	6.2	1.096774194			1.096774194
KC C	2	1.5	1.333333333			1.333333333
Mojave	9.6	5.6	1.714285714			1.714285714
McKee Springs A	0.8925	0.8656	1.03107671			1.03107671
MKS B	0.6659	0.5668	1.174841214			1.174841214
MKS C	0.7048	0.6078	1.159591971			1.159591971
MKS D	0.3705	0.3372	1.098754448			1.098754448
MKS E	1.0512	0.946	1.111205074			1.111205074
MKS F (chick)	0.2975	0.2412	1.233416252			1.233416252
MKS G	0.1429	0.1229	1.16273393			1.16273393
MKS H	0.3	0.276	1.086956522			1.086956522
MKS I	0.5325	0.379	1.405013193			1.405013193
Maharashtra, India	5.6	5.4	1.037037037			1.037037037
Jalisco, Mexico A	6	4.8	1.25			1.25
JM B	6.6	5.2	1.269230769			1.269230769
JM C	2.3	1.7	1.352941176			1.352941176
Bella Coola, BC Canada A1	0.3909	0.3625	1.078344828			1.078344828
BCBC A2	0.8611	0.7105	1.211963406			1.211963406
BCBC A3	0.221	0.157	1.407643312			1.407643312
BCBC B1	0.474	0.474	1			1
BCBC B2	0.9409	0.76	1.238026316			1.238026316
BCBC B3	0.2189	0.1401	1.562455389			1.562455389
BCBC C	0.8175	0.487	1.678644764			1.678644764
BCBC D	1.267	0.7443	1.70227059			1.70227059
BCBC E	0.47	0.442	1.063348416			1.063348416
Seton Creek, BC A1	0.0799	0.0645	1.23875969			1.23875969
SCBC A2	0.241	0.239	1.008368201			1.008368201
SCBC B	0.193	0.1459	1.322823852			1.322823852

SCBC C	0.11	0.0725	1.517241379			1.517241379
SCBC D	0.1667	0.159	1.048427673			1.048427673
SCBC E	0.18	0.1059	1.699716714			1.699716714
Hedley Cave, BC A	0.2	0.122	1.639344262			1.639344262
HCBC B	0.42	0.3847	1.091759813			1.091759813
Pavilion Lake, BC A	0.305	0.246	1.239837398			1.239837398
PLBC B	0.1019	0.0819	1.244200244			1.244200244
PLBC C	0.2478	0.2291	1.081623745			1.081623745
Chaco Canyon, NM A	0.9	0.6	1.5			1.5
CCNM B	2.1	1.5	1.4			1.4
CCNM C	2.6	2.2	1.181818182			1.181818182
CCNM D	1.6	1.55	1.032258065			1.032258065
CCNM E	0.9	0.71	1.267605634			1.267605634
CCNM F	0.9	0.8	1.125			1.125
CCNM G	2.7	2.55	1.058823529			1.058823529
CCNM H	4.8	4.8	1			1
CCNM I	6.7	6.3	1.063492063			1.063492063
Chongoni, Malawi A	1	0.8	1.25			1.25
CM B	3.35	3.3	1.015151515			1.015151515
CM C	4.2	3.9	1.076923077			1.076923077
CM D	5.3	5.3	1			1
Chinese Tiger Spiral	4	3.3	1.212121212			1.212121212
Chinese rock art A	0.2961	0.2365	1.252008457			1.252008457
CRA B	0.2462	0.205	1.20097561			1.20097561
CRA C	0.2192	0.175	1.252571429			1.252571429
CRA D	0.4821	0.462	1.043506494			1.043506494
CRA E1	0.243	0.203	1.197044335			1.197044335
CRA E2	0.428	0.425	1.007058824			1.007058824
CRA F	0.282	0.253	1.114624506			1.114624506
Haidian Egg Corona	0.9035	0.74	1.220945946			1.220945946
HE Sun	0.236	0.203	1.162561576			1.162561576
China rock Art G1	2.1	1.7	1.235294118			1.235294118
CRA G2 (duo/chick)	0.9	0.8	1.125			1.125

Charam	5.35	4.35	1.229885057				1.229885057
Bolivia A1	0.405	0.2639	1.534672224				1.534672224
Bolivia A2	0.6465	0.5775	1.119480519				1.119480519
Bolivia B1	0.3461	0.276	1.253985507				1.253985507
Bolivia B2	0.6235	0.5536	1.126264451				1.126264451
Alchemy	4.5	3.4	1.323529412				1.323529412
Aborigine A	3	2.3	1.304347826				1.304347826
Aborigine B	3.5	2.2	1.590909091				1.590909091
Aborigine C	2.2	1.5	1.466666667				1.466666667
Aborigine D	2.3	1.6	1.4375				1.4375
Aborigine E	6.6	5.9	1.118644068				1.118644068

Table 2 - % differences

(bold indicate possible hits)

%diff 1.001	%diff 1.05	%diff 1.07	%diff 1.1	%diff 1.15	%diff 1.17	%diff 1.21	%diff 1.25	%diff 1.35	%dif 1.5	%diff 1.70
22.25%	17.58%	15.68%	12.82%	8.06%	6.15%	2.34%	1.47%	10.99%	25.28%	44.32%
8.92%	4.25%	2.35%	0.51%	5.27%	7.17%	10.98%	14.79%	24.32%	38.60%	57.65%
5.35%	0.68%	1.22%	4.08%	8.84%	10.75%	14.56%	18.37%	27.89%	42.18%	61.22%
9.90%	5.23%	3.32%	0.47%	4.29%	6.20%	10.01%	13.82%	23.34%	37.63%	56.68%
14.85%	10.18%	8.28%	5.42%	0.66%	1.25%	5.06%	8.87%	18.39%	32.68%	51.72%
4.89%	0.22%	1.68%	4.54%	9.30%	11.21%	15.02%	18.83%	28.35%	42.64%	61.68%
27.59%	22.92%	21.02%	18.16%	13.40%	11.49%	7.68%	3.87%	5.65%	19.94%	38.98%
14.31%	9.65%	7.74%	4.89%	0.12%	1.78%	5.59%	9.40%	18.92%	33.21%	52.26%
23.16%	18.50%	16.59%	13.74%	8.97%	7.07%	3.26%	0.55%	10.07%	24.36%	43.41%
16.47%	11.80%	9.90%	7.04%	2.28%	0.37%	3.44%	7.25%	16.77%	31.06%	50.10%
23.71%	19.05%	17.14%	14.29%	9.52%	7.62%	3.81%	0.00%	9.52%	23.81%	42.86%
8.31%	3.64%	1.74%	1.12%	5.88%	7.79%	11.60%	15.41%	24.93%	39.22%	58.26%
9.33%	4.67%	2.76%	0.09%	4.86%	6.76%	10.57%	14.38%	23.90%	38.19%	57.24%
0.10%	4.76%	6.67%	9.52%	14.29%	16.19%	20.00%	23.81%	33.33%	47.62%	66.67%
10.73%	6.06%	4.16%	1.30%	3.46%	5.37%	9.18%	12.99%	22.51%	36.80%	55.84%
13.41%	8.74%	6.84%	3.98%	0.78%	2.69%	6.50%	10.31%	19.83%	34.12%	53.16%
49.06%	44.39%	42.49%	39.63%	34.87%	32.96%	29.16%	25.35%	15.82%	1.54%	17.51%
18.34%	13.67%	11.77%	8.91%	4.15%	2.24%	1.57%	5.38%	14.90%	29.19%	48.23%
27.11%	22.44%	20.54%	17.68%	12.92%	11.02%	7.21%	3.40%	6.13%	20.41%	39.46%
41.56%	36.90%	34.99%	32.13%	27.37%	25.47%	21.66%	17.85%	8.32%	5.96%	25.01%
14.62%	9.95%	8.05%	5.19%	0.43%	1.47%	5.28%	9.09%	18.62%	32.90%	51.95%
14.26%	9.59%	7.68%	4.83%	0.07%	1.84%	5.65%	9.46%	18.98%	33.27%	52.32%
45.76%	41.09%	39.18%	36.33%	31.57%	29.66%	25.85%	22.04%	12.52%	1.77%	20.82%

75.02%	70.36%	68.45%	65.59%	60.83%	58.93%	55.12%	51.31%	41.78%	27.50%	8.45%
0.10%	4.76%	6.67%	9.52%	14.29%	16.19%	20.00%	23.81%	33.33%	47.62%	66.67%
33.63%	28.97%	27.06%	24.21%	19.44%	17.54%	13.73%	9.92%	0.40%	13.89%	32.94%
16.84%	12.17%	10.26%	7.41%	2.65%	0.74%	3.07%	6.88%	16.40%	30.69%	49.74%
21.07%	16.40%	14.50%	11.64%	6.88%	4.97%	1.16%	2.65%	12.17%	26.46%	45.50%
30.06%	25.40%	23.49%	20.63%	15.87%	13.97%	10.16%	6.35%	3.17%	17.46%	36.51%
36.95%	32.29%	30.38%	27.52%	22.76%	20.86%	17.05%	13.24%	3.71%	10.57%	29.62%
31.61%	26.94%	25.04%	22.18%	17.42%	15.52%	11.71%	7.90%	1.63%	15.91%	34.96%
36.39%	31.72%	29.81%	26.96%	22.20%	20.29%	16.48%	12.67%	3.15%	11.14%	30.19%
32.19%	27.52%	25.62%	22.76%	18.00%	16.09%	12.28%	8.47%	1.05%	15.34%	34.38%
39.48%	34.81%	32.91%	30.05%	25.29%	23.38%	19.57%	15.76%	6.24%	8.05%	27.09%
44.94%	40.27%	38.37%	35.51%	30.75%	28.84%	25.04%	21.23%	11.70%	2.58%	21.63%
32.75%	28.09%	26.18%	23.33%	18.56%	16.66%	12.85%	9.04%	0.48%	14.77%	33.82%
1.01%	3.65%	5.56%	8.41%	13.18%	15.08%	18.89%	22.70%	32.22%	46.51%	65.56%
22.60%	17.93%	16.03%	13.17%	8.41%	6.51%	2.70%	1.11%	10.64%	24.92%	43.97%
12.74%	8.07%	6.17%	3.31%	1.45%	3.36%	7.17%	10.98%	20.50%	34.79%	53.83%
29.82%	25.15%	23.25%	20.39%	15.63%	13.72%	9.91%	6.10%	3.42%	17.71%	36.75%
178.01%	173.35%	171.44%	168.59%	163.82%	161.92%	158.11%	154.30%	144.78%	130.49%	111.44%
6.77%	2.11%	0.20%	2.66%	7.42%	9.32%	13.13%	16.94%	26.46%	40.75%	59.80%
11.39%	6.72%	4.82%	1.96%	2.80%	4.70%	8.51%	12.32%	21.85%	36.13%	55.18%
12.23%	7.56%	5.66%	2.80%	1.96%	3.87%	7.68%	11.49%	21.01%	35.30%	54.34%
13.28%	8.61%	6.71%	3.85%	0.91%	2.81%	6.62%	10.43%	19.96%	34.24%	53.29%
5.83%	1.16%	0.74%	3.60%	8.36%	10.27%	14.07%	17.88%	27.41%	41.69%	60.74%
3.54%	1.13%	3.03%	5.89%	10.65%	12.56%	16.37%	20.18%	29.70%	43.99%	63.03%
11.02%	6.35%	4.45%	1.59%	3.17%	5.07%	8.88%	12.69%	22.22%	36.50%	55.55%
11.57%	6.90%	5.00%	2.14%	2.62%	4.53%	8.34%	12.15%	21.67%	35.96%	55.00%
16.36%	11.69%	9.79%	6.93%	2.17%	0.27%	3.54%	7.35%	16.88%	31.16%	50.21%
1.47%	3.19%	5.10%	7.95%	12.72%	14.62%	18.43%	22.24%	31.76%	46.05%	65.10%

0.10%	4.76%	6.67%	9.52%	14.29%	16.19%	20.00%	23.81%	33.33%	47.62%	66.67%
29.74%	25.07%	23.17%	20.31%	15.55%	13.64%	9.83%	6.02%	3.50%	17.78%	36.83%
22.32%	17.65%	15.75%	12.89%	8.13%	6.22%	2.41%	1.40%	10.92%	25.20%	44.25%
20.31%	15.65%	13.74%	10.88%	6.12%	4.22%	0.41%	3.40%	12.93%	27.21%	46.26%
17.10%	12.43%	10.53%	7.67%	2.91%	1.00%	2.81%	6.62%	16.14%	30.43%	49.47%
21.35%	16.69%	14.78%	11.93%	7.16%	5.26%	1.45%	2.36%	11.88%	26.17%	45.22%
14.30%	9.63%	7.72%	4.87%	0.11%	1.80%	5.61%	9.42%	18.94%	33.23%	52.28%
71.97%	67.31%	65.40%	62.55%	57.78%	55.88%	52.07%	48.26%	38.74%	24.45%	5.40%
17.40%	12.73%	10.83%	7.97%	3.21%	1.31%	2.50%	6.31%	15.84%	30.12%	49.17%
9.47%	4.80%	2.90%	0.04%	4.72%	6.63%	10.44%	14.25%	23.77%	38.06%	57.10%
50.16%	45.49%	43.59%	40.73%	35.97%	34.06%	30.26%	26.45%	16.92%	2.64%	16.41%
13.13%	8.47%	6.56%	3.70%	1.06%	2.96%	6.77%	10.58%	20.11%	34.39%	53.44%
11.60%	6.93%	5.03%	2.17%	2.59%	4.49%	8.30%	12.11%	21.64%	35.92%	54.97%
4.51%	0.15%	2.06%	4.92%	9.68%	11.58%	15.39%	19.20%	28.73%	43.01%	62.06%
11.33%	6.67%	4.76%	1.90%	2.86%	4.76%	8.57%	12.38%	21.90%	36.19%	55.24%
21.88%	17.22%	15.31%	12.45%	7.69%	5.79%	1.98%	1.83%	11.36%	25.64%	44.69%
30.88%	26.22%	24.31%	21.45%	16.69%	14.79%	10.98%	7.17%	2.35%	16.64%	35.69%
15.38%	10.71%	8.81%	5.95%	1.19%	0.71%	4.52%	8.33%	17.86%	32.14%	51.19%
20.50%	15.83%	13.93%	11.07%	6.31%	4.40%	0.59%	3.22%	12.74%	27.03%	46.07%
13.97%	9.31%	7.40%	4.54%	0.22%	2.12%	5.93%	9.74%	19.26%	33.55%	52.60%
66.78%	62.11%	60.21%	57.35%	52.59%	50.68%	46.87%	43.07%	33.54%	19.26%	0.21%
17.63%	12.96%	11.06%	8.20%	3.44%	1.53%	2.27%	6.08%	15.61%	29.89%	48.94%
69.40%	64.74%	62.83%	59.97%	55.21%	53.31%	49.50%	45.69%	36.16%	21.88%	2.83%
42.23%	37.57%	35.66%	32.80%	28.04%	26.14%	22.33%	18.52%	8.99%	5.29%	24.34%
27.92%	23.25%	21.34%	18.49%	13.73%	11.82%	8.01%	4.20%	5.32%	19.61%	38.66%
29.21%	24.54%	22.64%	19.78%	15.02%	13.11%	9.30%	5.49%	4.03%	18.32%	37.36%
11.81%	7.14%	5.24%	2.38%	2.38%	4.29%	8.10%	11.90%	21.43%	35.71%	54.76%
13.67%	9.00%	7.10%	4.24%	0.52%	2.43%	6.24%	10.05%	19.57%	33.85%	52.90%

24.75%	20.08%	18.18%	15.32%	10.56%	8.65%	4.84%	1.04%	8.49%	22.77%	41.82%
19.61%	14.94%	13.04%	10.18%	5.42%	3.51%	0.30%	4.11%	13.63%	27.91%	46.96%
16.71%	12.04%	10.14%	7.28%	2.52%	0.62%	3.19%	7.00%	16.53%	30.81%	49.86%
17.76%	13.10%	11.19%	8.33%	3.57%	1.67%	2.14%	5.95%	15.48%	29.76%	48.81%
26.48%	21.82%	19.91%	17.05%	12.29%	10.39%	6.58%	2.77%	6.76%	21.04%	40.09%
29.84%	25.17%	23.27%	20.41%	15.65%	13.74%	9.93%	6.12%	3.40%	17.69%	36.73%
42.76%	38.10%	36.19%	33.33%	28.57%	26.67%	22.86%	19.05%	9.52%	4.76%	23.81%
29.46%	24.79%	22.89%	20.03%	15.27%	13.36%	9.55%	5.74%	3.78%	18.07%	37.11%
41.60%	36.93%	35.03%	32.17%	27.41%	25.51%	21.70%	17.89%	8.36%	5.92%	24.97%
16.41%	11.74%	9.83%	6.98%	2.22%	0.31%	3.50%	7.31%	16.83%	31.12%	50.17%
17.97%	13.31%	11.40%	8.54%	3.78%	1.88%	1.93%	5.74%	15.27%	29.55%	48.60%
0.07%	4.60%	6.50%	9.36%	14.12%	16.02%	19.83%	23.64%	33.17%	47.45%	66.50%
62.98%	58.32%	56.41%	53.56%	48.79%	46.89%	43.08%	39.27%	29.75%	15.46%	3.59%
3.57%	1.10%	3.00%	5.86%	10.62%	12.53%	16.34%	20.15%	29.67%	43.96%	63.00%
13.25%	8.59%	6.68%	3.82%	0.94%	2.84%	6.65%	10.46%	19.98%	34.27%	53.32%
33.67%	29.01%	27.10%	24.25%	19.48%	17.58%	13.77%	9.96%	0.44%	13.85%	32.90%
28.39%	23.72%	21.81%	18.96%	14.20%	12.29%	8.48%	4.67%	4.85%	19.14%	38.19%
10.21%	5.54%	3.64%	0.78%	3.98%	5.89%	9.70%	13.51%	23.03%	37.32%	56.36%
11.08%	6.41%	4.51%	1.65%	3.11%	5.02%	8.82%	12.63%	22.16%	36.44%	55.49%
0.80%	3.87%	5.77%	8.63%	13.39%	15.29%	19.10%	22.91%	32.44%	46.72%	65.77%
7.56%	2.89%	0.99%	1.87%	6.63%	8.54%	12.35%	16.16%	25.68%	39.97%	59.01%
15.94%	11.28%	9.37%	6.52%	1.75%	0.15%	3.96%	7.77%	17.29%	31.58%	50.63%
38.11%	33.44%	31.54%	28.68%	23.92%	22.01%	18.20%	14.39%	4.87%	9.42%	28.46%
10.13%	5.46%	3.56%	0.70%	4.06%	5.97%	9.78%	13.59%	23.11%	37.40%	56.44%
7.31%	2.64%	0.74%	2.12%	6.88%	8.79%	12.60%	16.41%	25.93%	40.22%	59.26%
8.56%	3.90%	1.99%	0.87%	5.63%	7.53%	11.34%	15.15%	24.68%	38.96%	58.01%
0.10%	4.76%	6.67%	9.52%	14.29%	16.19%	20.00%	23.81%	33.33%	47.62%	66.67%
45.35%	40.68%	38.78%	35.92%	31.16%	29.26%	25.45%	21.64%	12.11%	2.17%	21.22%

2.17%	2.49%	4.40%	7.26%	12.02%	13.92%	17.73%	21.54%	31.07%	45.35%	64.40%
19.67%	15.00%	13.10%	10.24%	5.48%	3.58%	0.23%	4.04%	13.57%	27.85%	46.90%
9.12%	4.45%	2.55%	0.31%	5.07%	6.97%	10.78%	14.59%	24.12%	38.40%	57.45%
31.65%	26.98%	25.08%	22.22%	17.46%	15.56%	11.75%	7.94%	1.59%	15.87%	34.92%
67.93%	63.27%	61.36%	58.50%	53.74%	51.84%	48.03%	44.22%	34.69%	20.41%	1.36%
2.86%	1.80%	3.71%	6.56%	11.33%	13.23%	17.04%	20.85%	30.37%	44.66%	63.71%
16.56%	11.89%	9.98%	7.13%	2.37%	0.46%	3.35%	7.16%	16.68%	30.97%	50.02%
15.10%	10.44%	8.53%	5.68%	0.91%	0.99%	4.80%	8.61%	18.13%	32.42%	51.47%
9.31%	4.64%	2.74%	0.12%	4.88%	6.79%	10.59%	14.40%	23.93%	38.21%	57.26%
10.50%	5.83%	3.92%	1.07%	3.69%	5.60%	9.41%	13.22%	22.74%	37.03%	56.08%
22.13%	17.47%	15.56%	12.71%	7.94%	6.04%	2.23%	1.58%	11.10%	25.39%	44.44%
15.40%	10.74%	8.83%	5.97%	1.21%	0.69%	4.50%	8.31%	17.83%	32.12%	51.17%
8.19%	3.52%	1.61%	1.24%	6.00%	7.91%	11.72%	15.53%	25.05%	39.34%	58.39%
38.48%	33.81%	31.91%	29.05%	24.29%	22.38%	18.57%	14.76%	5.24%	9.05%	28.09%
3.43%	1.23%	3.14%	6.00%	10.76%	12.66%	16.47%	20.28%	29.81%	44.09%	63.14%
23.71%	19.05%	17.14%	14.29%	9.52%	7.62%	3.81%	0.00%	9.52%	23.81%	42.86%
25.55%	20.88%	18.97%	16.12%	11.36%	9.45%	5.64%	1.83%	7.69%	21.98%	41.03%
33.52%	28.85%	26.95%	24.09%	19.33%	17.42%	13.61%	9.80%	0.28%	14.01%	33.05%
7.37%	2.70%	0.79%	2.06%	6.82%	8.73%	12.54%	16.35%	25.87%	40.16%	59.21%
20.09%	15.43%	13.52%	10.66%	5.90%	4.00%	0.19%	3.62%	13.15%	27.43%	46.48%
38.73%	34.06%	32.16%	29.30%	24.54%	22.63%	18.82%	15.01%	5.49%	8.80%	27.84%
0.10%	4.76%	6.67%	9.52%	14.29%	16.19%	20.00%	23.81%	33.33%	47.62%	66.67%
22.57%	17.91%	16.00%	13.15%	8.38%	6.48%	2.67%	1.14%	10.66%	24.95%	44.00%
53.47%	48.81%	46.90%	44.04%	39.28%	37.38%	33.57%	29.76%	20.23%	5.95%	13.10%
64.54%	59.87%	57.97%	55.11%	50.35%	48.44%	44.63%	40.82%	31.30%	17.01%	2.03%
66.79%	62.12%	60.22%	57.36%	52.60%	50.69%	46.88%	43.07%	33.55%	19.26%	0.22%
5.94%	1.27%	0.63%	3.49%	8.25%	10.16%	13.97%	17.78%	27.30%	41.59%	60.63%
22.64%	17.98%	16.07%	13.22%	8.45%	6.55%	2.74%	1.07%	10.59%	24.88%	43.93%

0.70%	3.96%	5.87%	8.73%	13.49%	15.39%	19.20%	23.01%	32.54%	46.82%	65.87%
30.65%	25.98%	24.08%	21.22%	16.46%	14.55%	10.75%	6.94%	2.59%	16.87%	35.92%
49.17%	44.50%	42.59%	39.74%	34.98%	33.07%	29.26%	25.45%	15.93%	1.64%	17.41%
4.52%	0.15%	2.05%	4.91%	9.67%	11.58%	15.39%	19.20%	28.72%	43.01%	62.05%
66.54%	61.88%	59.97%	57.12%	52.35%	50.45%	46.64%	42.83%	33.31%	19.02%	0.03%
60.79%	56.13%	54.22%	51.37%	46.60%	44.70%	40.89%	37.08%	27.56%	13.27%	5.78%
8.64%	3.98%	2.07%	0.78%	5.55%	7.45%	11.26%	15.07%	24.59%	38.88%	57.93%
22.75%	18.08%	16.17%	13.32%	8.56%	6.65%	2.84%	0.97%	10.49%	24.78%	43.83%
23.16%	18.50%	16.59%	13.73%	8.97%	7.07%	3.26%	0.55%	10.08%	24.36%	43.41%
7.68%	3.01%	1.11%	1.75%	6.51%	8.42%	12.23%	16.04%	25.56%	39.85%	58.89%
47.52%	42.86%	40.95%	38.10%	33.33%	31.43%	27.62%	23.81%	14.29%	0.00%	19.05%
38.00%	33.33%	31.43%	28.57%	23.81%	21.90%	18.10%	14.29%	4.76%	9.52%	28.57%
17.22%	12.55%	10.65%	7.79%	3.03%	1.13%	2.68%	6.49%	16.02%	30.30%	49.35%
2.98%	1.69%	3.59%	6.45%	11.21%	13.12%	16.93%	20.74%	30.26%	44.55%	63.59%
25.39%	20.72%	18.82%	15.96%	11.20%	9.30%	5.49%	1.68%	7.85%	22.13%	41.18%
11.81%	7.14%	5.24%	2.38%	2.38%	4.29%	8.10%	11.90%	21.43%	35.71%	54.76%
5.51%	0.84%	1.06%	3.92%	8.68%	10.59%	14.40%	18.21%	27.73%	42.02%	61.06%
0.10%	4.76%	6.67%	9.52%	14.29%	16.19%	20.00%	23.81%	33.33%	47.62%	66.67%
5.95%	1.28%	0.62%	3.48%	8.24%	10.14%	13.95%	17.76%	27.29%	41.57%	60.62%
23.71%	19.05%	17.14%	14.29%	9.52%	7.62%	3.81%	0.00%	9.52%	23.81%	42.86%
1.35%	3.32%	5.22%	8.08%	12.84%	14.75%	18.56%	22.37%	31.89%	46.18%	65.22%
7.23%	2.56%	0.66%	2.20%	6.96%	8.86%	12.67%	16.48%	26.01%	40.29%	59.34%
0.10%	4.76%	6.67%	9.52%	14.29%	16.19%	20.00%	23.81%	33.33%	47.62%	66.67%
20.11%	15.44%	13.54%	10.68%	5.92%	4.01%	0.20%	3.61%	13.13%	27.42%	46.46%
23.91%	19.24%	17.33%	14.48%	9.72%	7.81%	4.00%	0.19%	9.33%	23.62%	42.67%
19.05%	14.38%	12.47%	9.62%	4.85%	2.95%	0.86%	4.67%	14.19%	28.48%	47.53%
23.96%	19.29%	17.39%	14.53%	9.77%	7.86%	4.05%	0.24%	9.28%	23.56%	42.61%
4.05%	0.62%	2.52%	5.38%	10.14%	12.05%	15.86%	19.67%	29.19%	43.48%	62.52%

18.67%	14.00%	12.10%	9.24%	4.48%	2.58%	1.23%	5.04%	14.57%	28.85%	47.90%
0.58%	4.09%	5.99%	8.85%	13.61%	15.52%	19.33%	23.14%	32.66%	46.95%	65.99%
10.82%	6.15%	4.25%	1.39%	3.37%	5.27%	9.08%	12.89%	22.42%	36.70%	55.75%
20.95%	16.28%	14.38%	11.52%	6.76%	4.85%	1.04%	2.77%	12.29%	26.58%	45.62%
15.39%	10.72%	8.82%	5.96%	1.20%	0.71%	4.52%	8.33%	17.85%	32.14%	51.18%
22.31%	17.65%	15.74%	12.89%	8.12%	6.22%	2.41%	1.40%	10.92%	25.21%	44.26%
11.81%	7.14%	5.24%	2.38%	2.38%	4.29%	8.10%	11.90%	21.43%	35.71%	54.76%
21.80%	17.13%	15.23%	12.37%	7.61%	5.70%	1.89%	1.92%	11.44%	25.73%	44.77%
50.83%	46.16%	44.25%	41.40%	36.64%	34.73%	30.92%	27.11%	17.59%	3.30%	15.75%
11.28%	6.62%	4.71%	1.86%	2.91%	4.81%	8.62%	12.43%	21.95%	36.24%	55.29%
24.09%	19.43%	17.52%	14.67%	9.90%	8.00%	4.19%	0.38%	9.14%	23.43%	42.48%
11.93%	7.26%	5.36%	2.50%	2.26%	4.17%	7.97%	11.78%	21.31%	35.59%	54.64%
30.72%	26.05%	24.15%	21.29%	16.53%	14.62%	10.81%	7.00%	2.52%	16.81%	35.85%
28.89%	24.22%	22.32%	19.46%	14.70%	12.80%	8.99%	5.18%	4.35%	18.63%	37.68%
56.18%	51.52%	49.61%	46.75%	41.99%	40.09%	36.28%	32.47%	22.94%	8.66%	10.39%
44.35%	39.68%	37.78%	34.92%	30.16%	28.25%	24.44%	20.63%	11.11%	3.17%	22.22%
41.57%	36.90%	35.00%	32.14%	27.38%	25.48%	21.67%	17.86%	8.33%	5.95%	25.00%
11.20%	6.54%	4.63%	1.78%	2.99%	4.89%	8.70%	12.51%	22.03%	36.32%	55.37%

Most notable hits at 1.1 or 1.15, 1.35 and 1.5 for DR ratio differences.

Table 3 - Site Features

(this is messy so the author recommends opening the spreadsheet directly)

Site	Spiral	Chenige	Crescent/knife/boat	Cosmic Pole	Circle+D	2 layer	3 layer	4+ layer	Giant Man assoc.	hawk motifs	Jupiter-bands	mouth motifs	cabachon	long beam	"sunrise"	chicken egg	strong corona	flat egg	+dent	1 side ejection	dual	Eye motifs	Touching	Cross motifs	Flower Motif
Ramessees Stele A																X									
RS B		X							X																
RS C1																									
RS C2			X																						
RS D										X															
RS E										X															
RS F			X																						
Rameses II									X	X															
Chia Stele									X	X															
Maputo (big)																									
Maputo																									

VAU T C													X											
VAU T D								X		X														
VAU T E	X							X							X									
VAU T F													X										X	
VAU T G															X									
VAU T H								X	X															
VAU T I								X							X								X	
VAU T J						X																		
VAU T K																								
Thre e King s Pane l A																								
TKP B	X							X																
TKP C							X		X															X
TKP D		X	X																					X

Taz D																			X		X		
Taz E																X			X		X		
Taz F													X	X							X		
Taz G											X												
S America A1				X																			
SA A2		X									X												
SA B				X								X						X					
SA C																		X					
SA D																				X			
SA F											X												
Haida Copper A														X					X				
HC B														X									
Pennsylvania							X				X					X	X						
Onake Kindi, India A											X												

Table 4 - Modes and Averages

Mode	1	#N/A	#N/A	1.125	1.125	#N/A	1.25	1.25	#N/A	#N/A	#N/A
Avg	1.010014262	1.056349446	1.070687383	1.102400691	1.146935591	1.166971138	1.214651051	1.244374608	1.328720114	1.490899782	1.707398051
stdev list	1.26%	2.14%	2.30%	2.04%	2.47%	2.32%	2.50%	3.42%	5.80%	4.72%	4.37%
Stdev Mode and Avg	0.71%	#N/A	#N/A	1.60%	1.55%	#N/A	2.50%	0.40%	#N/A	#N/A	#N/A
% diff Mode and Avg	0.99%	#N/A	#N/A	2.05%	1.91%	#N/A	2.91%	0.45%	#N/A	#N/A	#N/A
% diff Rock Body	0.87%	5.22%	6.49%	9.18%	12.71%	14.21%	17.57%	19.54%	24.65%	32.85%	41.36%
% diff Jupiter	5.88%	1.23%	0.12%	3.00%	6.76%	8.36%	11.96%	14.06%	19.52%	28.27%	37.37%
% diff Saturn	9.76%	4.95%	3.54%	0.56%	3.34%	5.00%	8.73%	10.91%	16.57%	25.64%	35.07%
% diff Uranus	0.55%	3.86%	5.15%	7.88%	11.45%	12.97%	16.39%	18.39%	23.57%	31.88%	40.52%
% diff Neptune	0.15%	4.24%	5.52%	8.24%	11.80%	13.32%	16.72%	18.71%	23.87%	32.15%	40.76%
% diff Sun	0.99%	5.33%	6.60%	9.29%	12.81%	14.31%	17.67%	19.64%	24.74%	32.93%	41.43%

A corresponding Modes and averages and % differences table exists for the Site Features, but it is messy, so please see the original Spreadsheet.

us																									
% diff Nept une	12.9 2%	7.22 %	14.81 %	23.6 7%	16.5 3%	17.7 0%	8.38 %	8.38 %	14.6 4%	11.9 9%	15.5 2%	24.9 3%	20.9 5%	37.6 4%	18.8 0%	15.3 0%	17.5 6%	21.3 5%	16.2 7%	16.0 8%	19.4 3%	24.2 3%	16.3 0%	9.37 %	11.9 1%
% diff Sun	13.9 1%	8.28 %	15.78 %	24.5 4%	17.4 8%	18.6 4%	9.42 %	9.42 %	15.6 2%	12.9 9%	16.4 9%	25.7 9%	21.8 5%	38.3 5%	19.7 2%	16.2 7%	18.5 0%	22.2 5%	17.2 2%	17.0 4%	20.3 5%	25.0 9%	17.2 6%	10.4 1%	12.9 2%
% diff Ram esse s	6.28 %	13.2 4%	3.97%	6.84 %	1.88 %	0.45 %	11.8 2%	11.8 2%	4.18 %	7.42 %	3.11 %	8.38 %	3.52 %	23.8 8%	0.89 %	3.37 %	0.62 %	4.01 %	2.20 %	2.42 %	1.67 %	7.52 %	2.15 %	10.6 1%	7.51 %

(again bolded % indicate suspected "hits")

Summary

Looking across the data we see a number of resonant strikes, mostly with Jupiter, Saturn, and Neptune. We do not see hardly any resonant strikes in avg or % difference for Uranus, except at a very few sites. This supports the thinking that Uranus *arrived* and was not part of the formation process.

Plates (Example Scans)

This section to be filled in once scan copies are located/found. (Apologies from the author)

Most of the originals are contained in this folder

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1E6SFCcTTnGo2_BURfj3TS5mbjcMixDB?usp=sharing

One should be capable of producing similar results, even if the plates are lost forever (they shouldn't be).

Part 2 - The Big Picture

In this part, the author shall endeavor to re-create the timeline⁴⁵, with expected new knowledge overlaid with some Period data, and where possible, give exact datum. Bear in mind that we do not usually have any way to date, because even with written records such as the Enuma Elish, they were already myth and legend beforehand, and at any rate, no calendars would remain extant. Even with imperial Chinese records, which only date as far back as the Transition Period, there is great argument as to the veracity of the Chinese dating system⁴⁶. Although their method is more believable than the modern Sinologists, who attempt to compress everything into an Egyptologists' false timeline⁴⁷, we still see the problem of altered orbits and calendars, as Velikovsky noted in "Worlds in Collision." The bottom line is that *if* people could live 500 years or more in Biblical days, then how much shorter was our period around Saturn and then Jupiter assuming similar angular momentum? It's possible even day lengths were different to enable conservation of momentum. We've seen planets go around their stars in as little as a few days⁴⁸, or as long as thousands of years.

The Twin Motif /Twin Peaks/Pillars Motifs Emerge

The so-called "owl-eyes" in the egg research is inescapable. At first it is difficult to reconcile this, except to take DR measurements, for the sake of data collection. Then it becomes clear: when a *mitosis* of the star was to have occurred, what would be the expected condition or relationship immediately after? What also could cause them to become so interrelated that they were often regarded as brothers (with the Eldest not being king and the "superior" brother not being first born!⁴⁹), and later as husband and wife (as Kronos was castrated and turned female⁵⁰, and thus planet Saturn became Hera⁵¹)?

⁴⁵ Ibid. pp. 1-3

⁴⁶ https://www.reddit.com/r/AskHistorians/comments/5q5z7f/what_dating_system_did_the_chinese_use_prior_to/

⁴⁷ Now that we know the Great Pyramid preceded Khufu, the entire dating system of Egyptology is in question, or should be! <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-NB1XbAUjuA>

⁴⁸ <https://earthsky.org/space/pi-exoplanet-k2-315b-has-3-14-day-orbit/>

⁴⁹ Enki & the World Order lines 61-80 (Slide 5)

⁵⁰ Compare with the story of Alalu and Anu in the Song of Kumarbi Here is a summary "*The Kingship In Heaven* The Song of Kumarbi or Kingship in Heaven is the title given to a Hittite version of the Hurrian Kumarbi myth, dating to the 14th or 13th century B.C.E. It is preserved on three tablets, but only a small fraction of the text is legible and able to be translated.

This tale or song begins with how Alalu, the King of Heaven ruled for seven years and then is overthrown by Anu, who in turn rules for seven years before being overthrown by Kumarbi. This time, Kumarbi when he attacks his father Anu, Kumarbi bites off his genitals and when he spits it out, there were three new gods.

Okay then...

Anu tells Kumarbi that he is now pregnant with Teshub, Tigris and Tašmišu. When he heard this, Kumarbi spit out the semen to the ground and it became impregnated with two children. Kumarbi is then cut open, presumably by C-Section to deliver Teshub. Together, both Anu and Teshub then dispose of Kumarbi.

Knowing that history repeats itself and how Kumarbi overthrew his father Anu, just as he had overthrown his father Alalu; Kumarbi seeks out the goddess of the Sea (no name given) to see what to do to prevent his own demise.

The Sea tells Kumarbi to copulate with a rather large boulder, which then becomes pregnant and gives birth to a stone giant by the name of Ullikummi.

Once Ullikummi is born, he is taken to the Underworld and placed upon the shoulders of Ubelluris, the giant that holds up the earth. There, Ullikummi rises up like a pillar out of the sea. He is huge, some 9,000 leagues tall and 9,000 leagues in circumference.

Just huge. Worse, Ullikummi keeps on growing in size.

This worries the other gods who look to the trickster god Ea for advice on what to do. Ea says that Teshub should take the copper knife that had been used to split the heaven and earth at the beginning of time. Using the copper knife, Teshub sunders Ullikummi from Ubelluris, thus defeating him. With Kumarbi defeated, Teshub then takes his places as the new King of Heaven." <https://brickthology.com/2020/07/26/kumarbi/>

⁵¹ Hence Heracles; note that Mars, Earth and Saturn have nearly the same tilt angles.

It would be a **charge** relationship. Even though the twins split, they shared much of the same material, and some similar electrical needs. The Birkeland Currents which exist to this day between them⁵², and of course their moons would have been a serious amount of current flow and as we see on Earth, current causes objects to “glue” to one another through strong electrokinetic forces⁵³. It could very well have made a super-sized plasma sheath that was seen even much later as Earth was pulled away into the vicinity of Neptune. But at the time mentioned, the star’s electrical environment would have been shared by hundreds of bodies. It therefore became the origin of the Aesir and Vanir differentiation, when the two got further and further apart and bodies had to choose. After all the heroes belonged to either Zeus or to a goddess or to Poseidon... but never to two gods, except the trickster Loki (planet Venus) who also changed genders from time to time.

This is because in time they had to become completely differentiated. It should be expected that some other accretions, or more likely, *ejections* emerged from Jupiter (and maybe Saturn, beside Venus of course), given the number of sons Enlil has, and also their generally replicable rocky makeup. There is a lot of rocky and visual similarity between the Galilean moons, Mercury, and our Moon. Meanwhile Saturn’s own moons are more diverse and topologically unique. Jupiter does appear to have taken the lion’s share of mass as far as satellites go, and we see from its two different sets of prograde and retrograde moons that it must have taken some directly from Saturn, as well, (Osiris story?) and not only from the “father star.” There is still one moon

going prograde through its retrograde field^{54, 55}

Figure 7 - The chaotic and dangerous orbit presented would create havoc for shared satellites that used the center of mass for their initial attraction, then varying attractions to each body as they approached them. The whipping around would create devastating “high-carp floods” as the ancient text called them. **Note- click the paper link on title page for all animated gif options in this paper.**

The two revolved around each other at farther and farther distances, pulled apart perhaps by the Sun or momentum, or pushed by EMF. But nevertheless the Sun could not yet separate them forever. Instead, the emergence of the

⁵² Hence the change in Jupiter’s south pole changed to a hexagon as the planet’s began to approach each other for the 2020 conjunction

⁵³ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/22051020/>

⁵⁴ <https://www.space.com/41180-oddball-moon-orbits-jupiter.html>

⁵⁵ This by itself eliminates the Accretion model for solar system cosmogony completely.

planet Neptune added to the drama, first in its monstrous form, and then later as a god itself, moving in a unique 3-body motion.

Figure 8 - A temporary solution to the 3 Body motion, if bodies are of similar mass; note the acceleration.

Figure 9 - a triquetra like solution caused by the differential masses. Imagine this is the upper view of the spiral from Figure 7. Note that the small mass could be Earth or any other miniscule mass, but with there being literally hundreds, many of which are non-trivial, the actual orbit would be asymmetric both internal to the pairing, and externally.

Figure 10 - Worst case scenario when Neptune/Teshub emerges from Saturn or remnants of Shamash/Anu such as they were. The resultant G-forces placed upon the satellites of any of the bodies would be catastrophic and potentially deadly. Moreover the constant “nabbing” of their bodies would be seen as highly promiscuous, warlike (if thunderbolts occurred during transfer), and disloyal acts. It would appear to be a serious and critical drama, as seen in the Rig Veda, Upanishads, and Mahabharata.

Eventually the figure 8 would become a triquetra, and the triplet power was birthed and etched into the cultural DNA of mankind forever. After that, the formation became centered upon one body, and a conjunction of the

Awen or “peace” shape formed⁵⁶, and this was also immensely important, for it showed a “tree of energy” in the sky.

Figure 11 - Moreover the “levelness” of the orbit would be non-existent as we are used to in our solar system. First, the acceleration towards Sol/Apollo would be present, and an ever tightening orbit of the solar system’s center of mass. Secondly the electromagnetic forces we now see in galaxies inducing bend would be present. Finally, the kinetic momentum would be potentially chaotic, and gravitic

torque would also be present, as well as electrostatic attraction. If you are a satellite it would be a strange, difficult time. Bear in mind the smaller bodies should experience more acceleration, yet relative to the sun, all are small, and as the system itself approaches Sol, all would experience heavy torque and centrifugal forces.

The exchange of energy and plasma lasted for thousands of years, and a Golden Age of the gods⁵⁷ reigned. Things were not perfect, but the beginnings of agriculture, writing, and beer (and other drug use) began to merge with science, civilization, and culture. It was an enlightening age, relative to the preceding periods. It was, however, not to last, because of Hades/Satan/Set.

Figure 12 - LaGrange’s Solution to the 3 body problem⁵⁸

When the planet Uranus arrives in the story, it introduces a much needed antagonist to explain why the age had to end. Things go wrong, and now there is a reason. Depending on the source⁵⁹ Father Zeus does

⁵⁶ LaGrange’s Solution

⁵⁷ <https://www.greekboston.com/culture/mythology/golden-age/>

⁵⁸ Achieved when charge distribution reached a sort of equilibrium

⁵⁹ <https://www.quora.com/Why-did-Zeus-banish-Hades-from-Olympus>

eventually banish his “brother” to the Otherworld (Hades), and this banishment is deserved⁶⁰. But it was also the end of the good times in human reality. From then on out the father is a rover, a wanderer, a destroyer and trickster. He sleeps with mortal women, daughters, goddesses alike, birthing monsters and adventures. It is the time when the God of War becomes the primary hero⁶¹, and mankind suffers through a Transition Period down into an early Religious Period, to find meaning in the chaos.

What happens after that is not the topic of this paper. Instead, we are focusing on how by 5-6kya the Megafauna are largely extinct⁶² and all mammoths and mastodons are, even those in South America⁶³. The earliest Biblical stories were being told orally and possibly even compiled to explain catastrophic events such as the Deluge, and the Original Sin of mankind, wherein mankind loses the EDIN⁶⁴ and male and female begin to falter in relationships. These were chaotic times because there were still thunderbolts, and bolide impacts, and combinations of the two (thunderbirds). There was war, and death, and scarcity, and the rise of powers who fought against this by exceedingly worshiping the gods, and recreating over and over the vain Megalithic Period ideas that such worship could control the very orbits of the gods, and urge them to beneficence, instead of malevolence⁶⁵. Of course, they could not. It was always - as a matter of physics - going to break down. That didn't mean the roots of religion would disappear. It meant that we would move from pseudo-religion through early sciences (as mankind tried to predict and understand the gods, developing very sophisticated astrology and mathematics, even base 60 trigonometry⁶⁶), then swing back heavily to superstitious and organized religion as we tried to comprehend the great forces, especially the PEM, at work in the Heavens above which altered landscapes, weather, and destinies. Mostly the concept of God is revamped as a total explication of these phenomena, and a downplaying of the old gods or all of them occurred.

The first motif therefore, after the central point to the hexagon⁶⁷, to emerge is the twin peaks and pillars, which represent the holy mountains, as well as the greatness of these two first brother-gods⁶⁸. We see that they are themselves the representation of masculine strength, symbolized in arms. Their ability to lift great rocks, boulders, and even mountains, as well as wield the sword, spear, halberd, or cosmic bow and arrow, is unchallengeable⁶⁹. When they make war with each other (wrestling and shaking the world), or with demons or Hades himself, the great “weapons of Enki”⁷⁰ emerge and the world is destroyed in their wrath. To this day militarism is called “taking arms” and weapons are stored in an “armory.”

Eventually, by the time of the Shang Chinese, the Lord IS the thunderbolt/weapon as well as that Great Man which could uplift and control all 4 gas giants. Zurvan *is* the thunderbolt. Shiva *is* the vajra. They are Lord because they possess authority over life and death. But it is ultimately Jupiter/Enlil/Vishnu who sits upon the throne or Great Mountain, the motif which dominates the Megalithic Period with pyramids around the world.

*

⁶⁰ Yet Hades has this to say in response to Zeus' bragging, “No, no, great though he (Zeus) is, this that he has said is too much, if he will force me against my will, me, who am his equal in rank. Since we are three brothers born by Rheia to Kronos, Zeus, and I, and the third is Hades, lord of the dead men. All was divided among us three ways, each given his domain. I when the lots were shaken drew the grey sea to live in forever; Hades drew the lot of the mists and the darkness, and Zeus was allotted the wide sky, in the cloud and the bright air. But earth and high Olympos are common to all three. Therefore I am no part of the mind of Zeus. Let him in tranquility and powerful as he is, stay satisfied with his third share.” (Homer's Iliad, Book XV, ln. 184-195; translated by Richard Lattimore)”

⁶¹ Heracles, Gilgamesh etc.

⁶² <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-latin-america-55172063>

⁶³ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Notiomastodon>

⁶⁴ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Garden_of_the_gods_\(Sumerian_paradise\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Garden_of_the_gods_(Sumerian_paradise))

⁶⁵ In some cases they would withhold sacrifices and donations to the gods to “chastise” them for orbital madness.

⁶⁶ <https://arstechnica.com/science/2017/08/ancient-tablet-reveals-babylonians-discovered-trigonometry/>

⁶⁷ Meaning “sun” as far apart as Kentucky and China.

⁶⁸ As per Dave Talbott, “The Saturn Myth”

⁶⁹ Literally Saturn's South Pole.

⁷⁰ Meaning they were originally seen from Saturn, and now “borrowed” or “stolen” by Marduk or Enlil's sons (moons of Jupiter).

The Triquetra and IAO

This brings up a valid point. While the triquetra motion and the /|\ symbology of IAO (Yao/Yahweh/Ywahoo) represent the triple godhead⁷¹, the Lord of this period is without doubt the authority of Zeus/Odin/Jehovah/Horus and no longer Amen-Ra/Enki/Kronos, etc. Saturn's leadership is gone even by the time of the Deluge caused when Earth "touched Enki on his left side."⁷² It is Enlil who orders the destruction of mankind, and Enki is said to have saved mankind!⁷³ But it is Saturn's *rings* that were touched, not the planet itself. Consider, also, the role of the god of the Sea, and the destruction Neptune could bestow upon mankind while in an agitated state.

It becomes clear that the triform of the IAO is a re-visitation to the original three-body triquetra-like motion of the three gods, but now personified by Jupiter, Mars, and Venus, and no longer Saturn and Neptune. The repetition of the three in the Religious Period hearkens back to a more terrifying and inspiring time, seen in the DR measurements of rock art locations discussed above in Part 1 and around the world. But the inherited oral stories are from the end of the Megalithic when Jupiter is in full control, and in the Transition Period turned into something more "real" (abstract and anthropomorphic) in early pre-religion⁷⁴. In the Transition Period the gods become gay, mirth-like, tricksters, and can even be made fun of, but never trifled with or ignored. It would be reasonable in fact for Socrates to be put on trial for denying them and risking the state⁷⁵. Meanwhile plays could be written making light of the gods. But they could never be fully blasphemed. The trauma was much too recent, and after all Mars had only departed our vicinity, or us its, around the 2700 YBP boundary! A few

hundred years was not long enough for the Greeks to dismiss the gods altogether!

Figure 13 - Eagle Mound IAO/Awen⁷⁶, credit: Ohio Archaeological Council

The three-fold power motif or archetype has its origins in something more concrete than psychology. It is the revolving motion of dangerous, agitated, electrified, gaseous bodies still reeling from their creation under the strain and stress of

a flaring star, itself agitated by the approach of Sol! Greatness of power was in the air, after the fall of the Purple Sky and end of Zep Tepi. What replaced that central Creator God was a triplet of being which still mystifies Hindus to this day. Who to worship? Who not to worship? What are they worshipping? In the Judeo-Christian tradition this three-phase of power was replaced and forced into Unity, but its origins are just as confusing. Moshe (Moses) had the hardest time keeping the Hebrews from worshipping the planet Venus

⁷¹ "The Ancient Welsh Grammar...", John Williams et al., 1530-1606, Preface ix-xi

⁷² Ibid. lines 250-266 (slide 12)

⁷³ According to the "Atrahasis" text, Babylon

⁷⁴ Remember, it's hard to worship what you can no longer see readily above you.

⁷⁵ "The Apology," Plato, 399 B.C.E.

⁷⁶ The asymmetry of this has been covered in the first paper, in Part 1; however, you can clearly see it here, as well.

with a golden calf! He knew, as had the Greeks, that you could not trifle with the power of an Original God. With Neptune and Saturn by then departed for the far reaches of the new solar system 2.0, there was no reason to worship anybody other than Jupiter; it was Lord, for it represented the True Power of PEM. Certainly one should not “sin” by worshipping the moon, nor any other god! Psalms 82, 83, 85, and 89 make this very clear.

“82 God standeth in the congregation of the mighty; he judgeth among the gods.

2 How long will ye judge unjustly, and accept the persons of the wicked? Selah.

3 Defend the poor and fatherless: do justice to the afflicted and needy.

4 Deliver the poor and needy: rid them out of the hand of the wicked.

5 They know not, neither will they understand; they walk on in darkness: all the foundations of the earth are out of course.

6 I have said, Ye are gods; and all of you are children of the most High.

7 But ye shall die like men, and fall like one of the princes.

8 Arise, O God, judge the earth: for thou shalt inherit all nations.

83 Keep not thou silence, O God: hold not thy peace, and be not still, O God.

13 O my God, make them like a wheel; as the stubble before the wind.

14 As the fire burneth a wood, and as the flame setteth the mountains on fire;

15 So persecute them with thy tempest, and make them afraid with thy storm.

16 Fill their faces with shame; that they may seek thy name, O Lord.

17 Let them be confounded and troubled for ever; yea, let them be put to shame, and perish:

18 That men may know that thou, whose name alone is Jehovah, art the most high over all the earth.”

The IAO was not mere rays of light as has been suggested. It was shafts of electrical power and material (plasma? dust?) and *authority*. Coming from, primarily, the lower region of the tree at the stable end of the three-body problem (see LaGrange’s Solution above in Figure 12). It was this which formed the basis - ironically - of many monotheistic traditions. Three as one. This explains also the three faced motif⁷⁷. The five and the eight seen on that one, on its south and north poles, respectively. But the initiated knew about the six pointed star before this, and that the two brothers were originally one Lord: Elohim, Amen-Re, or Anu. So the

⁷⁷ A search via google images reveals a surprising array of disturbing images from around the world, and almost always a left face happy, middle face angry or a raging mask, and a right face as sad, distraught, etc.

secret of this knowledge was kept, but only among the wise, the priests, the chiefs, and the kings... and even then it was largely lost due to flood⁷⁸, war, Deluge, and volcanoes... or in the sands of destruction and time.

Figure 14 - Three-faced God motif, credit: Christoph Bacher

Origins of Sahara?

In the original paper, the author postulated that the moon's removed materials were the likely source of the Sahara and the Eye of the Sahara⁷⁹. This still remains probable, as Mars' dust is known to grow plant life, whereas moondust is not⁸⁰. However, there is another possibility that remains open. Since the changes that occurred there happened in the 7ky-5kya boundary⁸¹, it is possible, maybe even probable that the material is remnant moon material from the Moon destroying Kingu and other satellites⁸². Or, it may have streamed down from another Jovian body. In short, we cannot know (yet) precisely where the material came from, only that the volume of it is certainly foreign and irrational to be said to be simple desertification. It is clear looking at the Google Earth scans of the world that certain belts of locations, especially in Africa and the Middle East were affected by a massive cataclysm and marked by sudden and disastrous change that not even super volcanoes could replicate.

Figure 15 - Richat Structure aka "Eye of the Sahara", credit: USGS

⁷⁸ The Egyptian High Priest flat told Solon that the Greeks knew nothing and were like children again, because of the Deluge.

⁷⁹ From elevation and other geological features we can see this is not a manmade structure, but electrically carved.

⁸⁰ <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0103138>

⁸¹ <https://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2016/11/161130141053.htm>

⁸² "Enuma Elish," first tablet, <https://www.sacred-texts.com/ane/enuma.htm>

Figure 16 - Sahara fluvial patterns from Mediterranean to Atlantic (inverted color); source: Google Earth

Consider, for example, the megatsunami fluvial patterns across the Sahara. It's possible it could be an impactor but aside from there being no impactor crater of proportionate size in the Mediterranean, it doesn't seem possible to move that kind of volume of water without a concordant extinction event such as the Yucatan 65 Mya event. Since the fluvial pattern appears *since the formation of the desert*, it can only be concluded that either a massive upthrust (or unparalleled landslide) occurred which sent the water careening into the desert, leaving behind whale skeletons in Mauritania⁸³. Or, and maybe this is more in line with the evidence^{84 85 86}, that a sudden turning of the Earth upon the vertical axis til the poles flipped and the sun appeared to hang in the sky and go backwards⁸⁷, led to a massive wave⁸⁸. But it happened *since* the YD and Pulse 1 water rise. It happened in the last 7,000 years.

But, then we should see this pattern repeated world over. The flip occurred, but it doesn't seem to be the cause of the "high-carp flood", and this isn't Deluge flow, it's clearly a megatsunami. Logically it only makes sense, then, that a body came by, and lifted the water, and then moved it. We see again references to the Lord's power in Exodus and in the Psalms, and the ability to lift water (as well as make "the hills skip").

That means we have a new possibility based on the Exodus records: Venus. Venus very well could have brought the dust, and/or after the Moon destroyed the Sahara, lifted the water and then dumped it across the Sahara, leaving massive flooding. What this does for our understanding of the flood or floods is not to be

⁸³ <https://www.latimes.com/science/sciencenow/la-sci-sn-ancient-whale-africa-river-20150316-story.html>

⁸⁴ See: Adam and Eve Story" <https://www.cia.gov/library/readingroom/docs/CIA-RDP79B00752A000300070001-8.pdf>

⁸⁵ See author's previously mentioned paper on Jovian Octagons

⁸⁶ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1VPfZ_XzisU

⁸⁷ Joshua 10:13

⁸⁸ <http://www.bbc.com/earth/story/20170510-terrifying-20m-tall-rogue-waves-are-actually-real> If wind can do this... imagine

underestimated. Particularly in thinking not about Atlantis, as that was 12kya, but Dwarka in the Mahabharata, it is incredibly important; and other sunken lands in the 5kya boundary, such as Doggerland.

Or in the reasons for the widespread desolation on the western side of the continent of Australia; consider the possibility that Ayer's rock is the anode, and the Eye of Richat is the cathode... could there also have been a massive uplift of Mauritius and a subsequent collapse of "Lemuria"?⁸⁹ Too much speculation for the moment. We must confine ourselves to the frustration that without analysis of Venus' (or other moons of Jupiter or Saturn) surface composition, we will not solve the mystery completely. We will not know the precise mechanisms here. We can only speak based on the order of magnitude of the event, and the fact that it was super powerful, but not a massive world-ending extinction event. This is highly unusual (as are the suggestions that the Lord can lift mountains or destroy them in a single day, or even melt the hills⁹⁰!)

Heaven is Round, Earth is Square

One of the most classic sayings of ancient Chinese classics has always been interpreted in a spiritual and/or political tone, considering the "emperors" (before Qin), were often called the "little men,"⁹¹ as juxtaposed to the Great Man or Above God, Shang Di. Their purported humility was a religious as well as political statement of their role in the cosmic ethos as ruler and subject, together⁹². In this way, Heaven being round was thought by later thinkers to recognize the enigmatic and elusive power of the Creative force⁹³, and Earth being square to represent its limitations, and the statutes of order dictated from on high. In fact this is the reason that almost every single ancient Chinese city was built in a square, and had 4 gates for the four directions.

But when we come to the Amazon and the Ohio River valley we see a repetition of the concept in giant earthwork form. Moreover they are physically connected together. From the fact that sometimes instead of a circle we see an octagon, we can tell that there is some other meaning to this. It may be that there was a temporary "plasma sheet" or "current sheet"⁹⁴ upheld in space. At present the square is not easily identifiable. Some have said it is the flat earth (according to the perspective of agricultural people living on the ground) and this is not unreasonable. But the strange way that the circle and square are placed in offset, and proximity, even overlap, to one another suggests a more specific arrangement in the cosmos. We have already identified the octagons as belonging to the north pole of Jupiter, suggesting not only advanced astronomy and mathematics for the Allegewi but also that these are no mere hurricanes, but electrical storms which are held in perpetual⁹⁵.

Figure 17- Amazonian Earthworks, credit: Science⁹⁶

⁸⁹

https://www.academia.edu/36753644/Unboxing_Atlantis_A_top_down_review_of_what_we_know_and_dont_know_about_the_Atlantean_through_Megalithic_Period_continents_and_cities_36_000_2_000_YBP

⁹⁰ Psalm 97:5 "5 The hills melted like wax at the presence of the Lord, at the presence of the Lord of the whole earth."

⁹¹ See: "The Book of History" 書經 and "Canon of Shun" 舜典 for examples

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Emperor_Shun

⁹² https://www.academia.edu/33852373/Who_Answered_the_Shang_Diviner_The_Nature_of_Shang_Divination

⁹³ Compare these ideas to the Zhou Yi (I Ching), #1 Heaven, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1396853>, commentary by Confucius etc.

⁹⁴ <http://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1086/303824/pdf>

⁹⁵ In fact the Allegewi were so good at identifying the storms they could even note which one was weak or wavered, by aligning one mound to not face the center as the other 7 did.

⁹⁶ <https://www.sciencemag.org/news/2017/02/these-giant-mysterious-carvings-had-surprisingly-little-impact-environment>

We must bear in mind that the Babylonians, probably via the Sumerians, knew that at one time the Heavens and Earth separated, for it is in the Gilgamesh that we encounter in this enigmatic line⁹⁷. It has little religious meaning, except through abstraction. But cosmologically speaking, it could be stupendously important!

Amazonia, Kithiki, Connected in more ways than one

Yet what really amazes one is the fact that the religion of the area was shared not only across the Atlantic between the Khumry and Allegewi (did they have a shared origin in terms of diffusion?), but that technology vis-a-vis terra-preta (dark earths) appears to have been taken from Kithiki (circa the Green and Tennessee rivers) to the Amazon itself⁹⁸. It may mark a thousands of years transition, OR more possibly, that after the YDE, Amazonians were forced to flee the South American plateau, and make their way north to the Great River and on into Kithiki, taking with them the Kentucky Coffee Tree (which has hitherto had mysterious origins⁹⁹). There they perhaps re-learned agriculture or tried to make the Kentucky soil as rich in tree production as the Amazon had been. Later, after the arrival of Ameroindians and the decline of the Archaic Indians during the Megalithic, they may have fled south again, eventually coming to the ancestral homeland of Brazil. This would possibly explain the Virocochan tradition as well as anything, for if they were a people connected at all to the Khumry or Atlanteans, and there was a transfer of technology during the Transition Period, it would seem that they could both seed the Allegewi and the Amazonians of the AD era! But whatever the reasons, they also believed, as did the Shang of China, that Heaven is round, and Earth is square. As for why Earth - the Receptive - is square, it is not yet perfectly clear. The Columbian rock art¹⁰⁰ will probably be revelatory. Until then, all the speculation is only early and of course, highly speculative.

The Hammered Bracelet

The mainstream of science is replete with hopes¹⁰¹ and examples of theories¹⁰² of asteroid and comet seeding onto the Earth¹⁰³. What's odd is this is clearly catastrophism, but for some reason archaeologists and astronomers are not scientific enemies. Regardless, there is a real reason for this obsession: practically every aboriginal and religious culture around the world has a memory of the "Thundereggs"¹⁰⁴ and eras of destruction by "fire and brimstone."¹⁰⁵ Now, there still is a continual barrage of rocks and bolide, meteor showers, etc, even to this day. But the evidence and persistence of dolmens and cave cultures suggests that there was more at the time.

Some of this is clearly arc discharge excavation of the Moon and Mars, but there is now clear evidence for destroyed planetoids forming the asteroid belts, particularly the main belt¹⁰⁶. Thus when Velikosky wrote "Worlds in Collision" he was on the nose in a case or two¹⁰⁷. Particularly we are interested in the

⁹⁷ "Gilgamesh" lines 1-26, <https://etcsl.orinst.ox.ac.uk/section1/tr1814.htm>

⁹⁸ https://www.academia.edu/39821083/Amazonia_Kentucky_Connection_excerpts_from_AKHA_articles

⁹⁹

<https://www.courier-journal.com/story/life/home-garden/2017/07/28/kentucky-coffee-tree-evolutionary-anachronism-anyone/513434001/>

¹⁰⁰ If they will ever release the entire 8 miles of art to the public!

¹⁰¹ <https://www.nationalgeographic.com/science/article/120928-life-meteors-earth-slow-astrobiology-science>

¹⁰² <https://blogs.scientificamerican.com/guest-blog/did-the-seeds-of-life-come-from-space/>

¹⁰³ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Panspermia>

¹⁰⁴ <https://richardsonrockranch.com/story-of-the-thunderegg/>

¹⁰⁵ <https://www.ancient-origins.net/news-history-archaeology/sodom-meteor-0011030>

¹⁰⁶

https://www.academia.edu/38560727/Birkeland_Polyphase_Superweb_A_Proposition_for_the_Future_Betterment_of_Mankind_global_defense_interconnection_and_unlimited_power Figure 9, pp.8

¹⁰⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LDVeyk3a0Es>

disappearance of Metis¹⁰⁸, and also the death of Baldr (the Brave) and subsequent banishment of Hodr¹⁰⁹,

which appears to maybe be Triton in retrograde around Neptune. So what caused these collisions?

Figure 18 - Triton's Retrograde orbit (one of several mysteries that debunk SM formation theories¹¹⁰); credit: plutorules.com¹¹¹

It's not possible in the current arrangement, nor in the conjunction arrangements [whether they be collinear or coplanar^{112 113}]. **Only the three body problem explains the**

chaos, and the arrival of Nemesis/Black God/Planet X/Hades/Set.

Setting aside the oddball planet Uranus, we can see that there is a high likelihood that as host planets Saturn and Jupiter moved further apart into an analemma motion and then with Neptune into an oblong triquetra, and finally into the stable LaGrange arrangement, we would see an increasing possibility of a few actual kinetic collisions. If the Earth moved through the debris field: thundereggs. If there is arc excavation and subsequent hurtling towards the Earth: thundereggs. If there are gravity slingshotting of asteroids afterwards, from the accelerating system (towards the Sun) by Jupiter or other gas giants: thundereggs.

It can be expected then, that there were needs for dolmens and caves outside of just the Megalithic Period, but also through the Tepe, Archaic, and Transition Periods. This continual reminder was made all the worse by the Great Comet Venus¹¹⁴, and remained a fear all the way til this day when even eclipses capture awe and inspire doom and gloom prophecies on the internet.

However, the concept of a *hammered* bracelet, and its reminiscence to Thor's belt of power¹¹⁵, gives us some hint of two more precise relationships: Jupiter's thunderbolts or Mars' very body being excavated. Given the Asteroid Belt is located between Jupiter and Mars, it may very well be that there was a collision in the region *as well as* Jupiter's thunderbolts excavating Mars itself. There aren't any clear myths of Zeus punishing Heracles, however, so the Venus-Mars "collision" (arc discharge) remains more likely.

Later in the circa 2700 YBP boundary, Mars' red dust came down onto our planet, and to this day Earth can induce Mars to have planet-wide dust storms. But this period should not be confused with the harder

¹⁰⁸ "The Theogony"

<https://www.quora.com/In-the-Theogony-when-Zeus-eats-Metis-due-to-a-prophecy-that-she-will-bear-a-son-that-will-be-even-more-powerful-than-he-it-says-But-Zeus-put-her-into-his-own-belly-first-that-the-goddess-might-devise-for-him-both>

¹⁰⁹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/H%C3%B6r%C3%B0r>

¹¹⁰

https://www.academia.edu/40178988/EPEMC_Opinion_Editorial_Haumea_Ring_Destroys_Accretion_Model_Why_the_Accretion_Model_AM_is_inadequate_for_ring_formation_as_demonstrated_by_Haumea_favoring_the_electromagnetic_Coalescence_Model

¹¹¹ <https://anastrogeek.wordpress.com/2017/12/14/the-rebellious-moontriton/>

¹¹² <https://news.yale.edu/2019/03/04/case-over-tilting-exoplanets>

¹¹³ <https://arxiv.org/abs/1301.0446>

¹¹⁴ <https://agupubs.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/2013JA019164>

¹¹⁵ Meginjörð, See: "Prose Edda" <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Meginj%C3%B6r%C3%B0>

catastrophe of the fire and brimstones, which had to precede 4kya, as there are not very many references in the Torah. Therefore, we see that the majority of the thundereggs were created during the Clash of the Titans or “war of the holy families,” such as seen in the Mahabharata.

The meaning of hammer, however, does connect to Jupiter more directly: the Chinese word (as is covered in a previous paper¹¹⁶) for “to beat” means hammer, and “shock” means “earthquake”, and is commonly translated as “Thunder.” The plasmaglyph for Thunder is, of course, the Great Man. So we see that the original wielder of Mjolnir (the thunderbolt) is Odin.¹¹⁷

The Intestines and Wolves in the Sky

One thing the “Enki and the World Order” makes explicitly clear is that the motif known as the Intestines Hanging in a Tree, is **not incorrect**. Firstly the intestines are the innards of Shamash, described as “inscrutable” and “terrible to behold” and at the same time awe-inspiring¹¹⁸. The tree, of course, was the plasma streaming between the cosmic bodies in a conjoined formation. These bodies were in an early arrangement, but they must have formed an earlier LaGrange arrangement or similar, between the mother star (considered

Father) and the two other gas bodies, and perhaps some of the larger satellites like Mars or Mercury¹¹⁹.

Figure 19 - Black Dragon Canyon, Utah; credit: climb-utah.com¹²⁰

This is a wholly different matter, as far as we can tell than the wolf or coyote motif, which appears to be a plasma sheath flare, or any other form of plasmaglyph which has itself been recorded many times over on the rock art ¹²¹. The intestines have also been recorded mostly as zig zag patterns (caused by orbit and rotation), which stream across the sky in many rock art panels such as in Columbia, Australia, or at Newspaper Rock in Utah. Why should the innards of the star not be cause for both terror and awe? Almost certainly radiation exposure

would have increased, and diseases followed. At the same time it would have been difficult to look away from the sky above.

It can possibly be postulated that it was the early “tree” that was seen which constituted the actual body of the Great Man, and not a mere Peratt Synchrotron Instability¹²², as he and others have postulated. Maybe that plasma form was seen over and over and helped cement the motif. It is not knowable explicitly at this time.

¹¹⁶ https://www.academia.edu/38268897/Sumo_Ancient_Ritual_to_the_Thunder_God

¹¹⁷ It is important to note that Odin is pronounced “Othin” as in the th rune, for thunder.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=b12NUpmcfw8>

¹¹⁸ Ibid., slide 10 again; note the reference to diadems/crowns and putting them on kings’ heads. This means humans of course, but possibly also Neptune and Uranus

¹¹⁹ Based upon astrology, it would be reasonable to be: Mars, Mercury, Jupiter, Saturn, and Venus later

¹²⁰ <https://climb-utah.com/SRS/srra.htm>

¹²¹ <https://www.angelfire.com/trek/archaeology/coyote.html>

¹²² <https://link.springer.com/content/pdf/bfm%3A978-1-4612-2780-9%2F1.pdf>

The reason we can postulate this is that several of the Great Man motifs don't involve round heads, but birds ("ducks"), which as noted before was an early shape associated with the star's dying pangs. So if the motif altered or repeated as the star changed, it can be surmised as well that the orbits around it caused changes (as well as Sol's spiralling approach), and that the star appeared to change, as did the motif. This would explain a great many variations of therianthrope imagery often placed in proximity to the Great Man motif on rock art. Again consider Newspaper Rock or Columbia, et al.

Figure 20 - Duckhead Man; credit: grahamhancock.com¹²³

The Headless, Exploding Deer aka a Five-legged Turtle?

The appearance in most of the world of an exploding-out-the-back deer, horse, or other 4 legged animal seems quite distinct from the 5 legged turtle or 5 legged "alligator" rock art or mound (Figure 21).¹²⁴ But if we understand the sequence it utmost, pressures interior to it must have come a magnificent on the top moved into a dorsal exploded. Based on one site a two-eyed or "owl-eyed" alien zapped the ground where the died. This is precisely the paper 1 and Addendum 1, and Chief to Thomas Jefferson!¹²⁵ and despite the racist

isn't. As the star was stretched to its preparing for a mitosis-like split, there CME moment where the "hatchling" position of the motif, and quite literally in Utah, the followup to this was that like tall man, then reached and animals were, and they, of course, postulate of the Megafauna Extinction supports the words of the Delaware Also it supports the Navajo stories¹²⁶, assumptions of western archaeology,

natives did not simply all share the same stories. They had quite distinct cosmogonies and myths. As far apart as the Delaware and Navajo were, it is not to be expected that one influenced the other. Besides which, the story of the destruction of the "evil animals" and "evil people" extends to South America and beyond, as well.

So what was this Coronal Mass Ejection caused by? The author believes it can only either be a sudden lurching motion towards Sol, or similarly, if Sol was a binary star already with Shamash, then internal pressures within Shamash that suddenly flared. Maybe due to relative position around the Local Chimney, measured of course anciently in relation to the Pleiades constellation¹²⁷. It was not, however, as has been erroneously postulated elsewhere a solar "micronova." This is a false (or safe) interpretation which ignores all other lines of evidence to get down to the nitty gritty of flares. But the headless exploding deer completely challenges this.

First the motif is a continuation of an evolving situation where the DR is now beyond 2.0 and quite arced. Secondly in the motif, the "belly" has become the back of the deer, and instead of a pig or lion's torso,

¹²³ <https://grahamhancock.com/phorum/read.php?1.1036565.1064718>

¹²⁴ See: pp. 42, 45 for Holy Cow glyph and Tolar glyph https://www.academia.edu/36753645/On_the_Origins_of_Religions

¹²⁵ "In Search of Ice Age Americans," K Tankersley, p 51-52, or see the first paper, page 2

¹²⁶ Erdoes and Ortiz, 1984, again see first paper, page 3

¹²⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Gza1pEjRX6Y>

the legs now stretch out both in front and behind, and the explosion is completely dorsal. Meaning the observation was made at a different point in the year than the etchings at Gobekli Tepe, which were probably done around the same seasonal time each time, either because of needs of food, or perhaps a holiday ritual (early Saturnalia?) Either way, the belly became a back, and the DR is not 1.0 such as at the sun but beyond 2.0, which makes it **impossible to be a Solar micronova**. It was the first explosive flare of a dying Father God/birthing God-dess. Again see the “Song of Kumarbi” and “Enki and the World Order.”

Figure 22 - The moving star (bird) and then morphing into “boar”... note the features that remain

Figure 23 - Lion motif, the star is now stretched well beyond 2.0 and the same features remain (legs, mouth), but the interpretation of the god is one of becoming like a lion. Think about the Sphinx, and of the identification of the flaring god in Hinduism, with the many arms, each holding something (much of it destructive) and ripping at the innards of a lesser god (see Figure 24 below)

Conjunctivitis

Mankind is predisposed to look for patterns. Much of what was interpreted has been re-interpreted. Some Nazca lines are said to be orcas, or sharks, or hummingbirds. Except that hummingbirds are tiny, and the thunderbird of Peru is gigantic, perhaps one of the largest such motifs in the world!

Similarly, when mankind - to this day - sees an alignment, he imagines all sorts of meaning and symbology, both good and evil. It is no different than in the ancient days. First there is the question of the implausible “Talbotian” co-linear conjunction involving Earth, Mars, Venus, Saturn, and at least Jupiter, maybe more. But we must remember three things about the conjunction:

1. All of them are interpretations of images and those images, usually rock art, are representations of a single moment that we can prove. In Kentucky that moment

involves one excellent bass-relief in stone of a single orb, and a hexagon, probably Saturn's South Pole.¹²⁸

2. As we were pulled behind our host (Saturn), very frequently if it moved fast we could have been held in *relative* conjunction throughout an acceleration, and this would have been remarkable enough to record, even if it was temporary.
3. We must accept and account for either a coplanar conjunction with Jupiter, or in fact some other orbit which *discounts the Talbottian conjunction* nearly completely because we already know our northern hemisphere faced south and passed over the north pole of Jupiter, which has barely changed in 5,000 years. This cannot be accounted for in any other way without giving the natives telescopes in their history.

So we are left to wonder at the 'conjunction obsession.' Probably it was many forms of conjunction, such as the Triforce in the Awen /|\ and the triquetra, and the analemma, etc. Probably anything symmetrical, especially associated with certain holy times of the year, would have been a cause to make a record. For example when Jupiter was the Great Mountain alone, and some type of light extended down from it, then there was cause to revitalize the Saturnalia tradition of a "Christmas tree" which to this day is drawn with a step pyramid like conical Z-pinch towards a 5 pointed star (Jupiter's South Pole). This tradition is roughly 5,000 years old. Saturnalia, however, is clearly older than that.¹²⁹

Figure 25 - Jupiter's South Pole changed from a 5 pointed star to 6, in November 2019 as the Saturn/Jupiter conjunction began approaching. The effect of this was non-trivial as many world problems, including the COVID-19 pandemic, became pronounced beginning from that point; credit: NASA/Juno

The one conjunction that is remembered is the Great Comet Venus' eclipsing of the sun just prior to the destruction by Medusah/Kali, and this kind of conjunction keeps alive the repetition of fear, awe, and hope in spiritual circles, that was inspired by something truly terrifying. No regular eclipse can explain this behavior and irrational fascination, in this author's opinion.

¹²⁸ "On the Origins"... page 42, credit: Coy & Fuller, et al.

¹²⁹ Yet it is remembered each winter as Christmas, because the Chrissus messiah of ancient Egypt going back 4,600+ years as a prophecy was associated with the son of the Heavenly Father, Jehovah/Jove/Jupiter. Is this conjunction remembered? Only in motif and in practice, but not in cultural discussion.

The Mask, or Terror of Clowns

There's no way to talk about irrational fascination and horror without mentioning the happy-sad clown motif, covered in a previous paper on Theme Parks and the Dionysian therapy they provide.¹³⁰ This motif is, of course, related to the worldwide mask tradition, which especially in the East focuses on the excitingly terrific and horrifying expressions of the Devil, demons, or other terrifying entities which play tricks (coyote again), and rip people to pieces. To this day children wear Freddy and Jason masks at Halloween and pretend to eviscerate each other.

Looking back at a previous paper on Shang Di, Heaven, and Dao, we see that the mask motif originally was the Great Man, with a "maltese" cross motif (meaning a planet-star), with outstretched claw hands which resemble a form of lightning.¹³¹ Imagining this from above, one cannot help but be reminded of the horror of a child beholding a father's face turning to a "mask of rage" and of course various Renaissance paintings depict this exact child-like behavior in people fleeing from destruction from the Heavenly Father.

Figure 26: Babel History of the Tower of Babel (series title) Theatrum Biblicum; credit: alamy.com

What was the mask? We cannot tell, but possibly it was a sudden change in brightness or coloration of the star, which may have dimmed the atmosphere and produced a spooky glow, accompanied by a pair of

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https://www.academia.edu/37403915/Ferris_Wheels_and_the_Dionysian_Irony_The_subconscious_drive_of_thrill_abandonment_of_caution_and_the_motifs_of_Amusement_Park_rides

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https://www.academia.edu/39776252/Ancient_Origins_of_Taijiquan_Do_plasmaglyphics_belie_a_more_ancient_origin_of_the_internal_martial_art_of_Taijiquan_An_EP EMC_Analysis

thunderbolts.¹³² Perhaps it was an eclipse which did this, and the planet passed too near to a planet-star, it isn't exactly clear from the age of the Chinese glyphs and the tradition. It may be more likely a Venus related motif than Saturnian or Jovian. Nevertheless, it does represent an ancient tradition of God overthrowing demons and devils, in a psychological and yet physical battle mankind witnessed. Many variations of this tradition of the protagonist defeating or even destroying the devil exist, including the Ramayana and the Horus tale. But what is key is that there is a relationship between the happiness of the mask, and the sadness, even psychological terror "It" produces, even to this day, and which is maintained¹³³.¹³⁴

Hermes/Mercury and Venus are sent by Thunderbolt

Right now, the mainstream is reconfiguring to include concepts of electromagnetism controlling the cosmos instead of gravity.¹³⁵ Major *shocks* are coming, as they are realizing Dark Energy is likely not real¹³⁶, and where there is magnetism, there is electricity.¹³⁷ Now there exists footage of experiments involving magnetic phase locking without superconductivity, created by sufficient rotation of magnetic fields. Therefore, if there is any surprise that is no longer a surprise, it is that the Greek concepts of "messengers" and Zeus sending gods away, perchance towards the Sun, may be a literal issue of the transfer of charge via large bodies.

Think about this, as well, there is now established satellite experimentation and testing on both comets and asteroids, and as it turns out, there is no real difference between them compositionally.¹³⁸ They both tend to be dual lobes, one larger than the other (just like Saturn and Jupiter), and they are both made of rock, which inexplicably excavates resulting in spontaneous shrinking of the body.¹³⁹ However, comets remain in intense elliptical orbits, while asteroids are either in belts or erratic.

It appears that the difference may be whether or not they have been touched by thunderbolt and thereby "sent" as a messenger towards the sun, or other gods, whatever the case may be. It was never made clear in the myths (to the author's knowledge) why Hermes was both a watcher and a messenger/aid to Zeus. In Egypt Thoth becomes known as the wisest and most knowledgeable god, as well. Is this because Mercury was sent towards the sun, where light comes from? Looking at the myth of Heimdallr, we see that his mother is many monsters (whereas Loki is the mother of many monsters), and is a god of "a thousand eyes." This is clearly a reference to the hyper-pocked surface of Mercury, but are these "eyes" gouged out by the many monstrous mothers, and are they also seen as a source of knowledge and insight? Unclear. But it does appear that Hermes-Thoth was sent towards the sun fairly early in the Jovian era, and doesn't figure into the later stories.¹⁴⁰ Was it part of what brought the Moon, almost certainly another Jovian body, to the Earth? Much research into stories related to Mercury are needed to be certain; or at least to continue the speculation.

¹³² Consider the transistor behaviors of electric stars <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JsfEG4HzWAY>

¹³³ Again, refer to the three-faced-God motif.

¹³⁴ <https://childmind.org/article/helping-kids-creepy-clown-epidemic/>

¹³⁵ "Electric Currents in Geospace and Beyond," 2017, Wiley is an example; as are numerous articles such as <https://www.quantamagazine.org/physicists-identify-the-engine-powering-black-hole-energy-beams-20210520/>

¹³⁶ <https://www.futurity.org/dark-energy-dark-matter-universe-expansion-2543202-2/#:~:text=Researchers%20know%20that%20dark%20energy.attracting%20a%20south%2Dseeking%20pole.>

¹³⁷ <https://www.nature.com/articles/150405d0> "If a conducting liquid is placed in a constant magnetic field, every motion of the liquid gives rise to an E. M. F. which produces electric currents. Owing to the magnetic field, these currents give mechanical forces which change the state of motion of the liquid. Thus a kind of combined electromagnetic-hydro-dynamic wave is produced which, so far as I know, has as of yet attracted no attention. The phenomenon may be described by the electro-dynamic equations" ~Hannes Alven

¹³⁸ They are both made up of rock; icy comets have not been empirically and directly observed, only speculated about. A Actual probe results show a rocky composition.

¹³⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=34wtt2EUToo>

¹⁴⁰ <https://www.theoi.com/Olympios/HermesFamily.html>

Part 3 - Ages of Ice and Heat

In this part we will examine a new, exciting potential possibility for the sudden emergence of the ice ages, and for their disappearances, which is almost just as inexplicable.

The Most Willful Ostriching in Geology

There are loads of colorful, cute climatologist theories about the ice ages. They range from carbon dioxide variation¹⁴¹ to ocean current speculation¹⁴² (of course with no real data), to comets and volcanoes (one of the cutest theories¹⁴³, as will be explained later), and the big speculation which has only recently begun and isn't completely off, but is also without any ease of explanation from SM: solar variation. There is no mechanism in gravity-based-fusion for solar variation, nevertheless, speculators abound.

But the most obvious answer, which is verboten in geology, astronomy, and Science in general, but which is most clear and simple, is that the planet's tilt and/or orbit has changed.¹⁴⁴ This is the simplest fact to review, and as it turns out there is some rather straightforward data to discuss this¹⁴⁵.

It all starts with flash frozen mammoths^{146, 147} whose stomachs contain undigested food¹⁴⁸, and whose steaks were edible right out of the ice¹⁴⁹. What is most astounding is the variety of plants contained within the stomachs, which are no longer even found in the regions of Siberia where the mammoths are frozen!¹⁵⁰

Secondly, we have the Ohio Valley mound data which shows clearly enough that even if the Earth was not orbiting Jupiter, it would be required to have a position in orbit to enable telescopes (if those can be allowed) to view directly to the north pole of Jupiter!¹⁵¹ Of course no such telescopes existed, and it's obvious the Earth was upside down¹⁵², therefore the direction the sun appeared to move was opposite, and that we even passed over Jupiter's north pole. This is not a matter for dispute, as the data is precise¹⁵³ and mathematically sound.

So why is it that geology does not want to discuss the fact that the orbit of Earth clearly had to have changed, at periodic times¹⁵⁴? There is an untenable, on its face ridiculous dictum in astronomy that the solar system cannot change quickly, and hasn't changed in arrangement for 4 billion years¹⁵⁵. This is, of course, complete rubbish. The solar system is moving all the time, and changing all the time. There is nothing permanent about the entire Universe. Even in the space era, we have seen brightness changes in stars, galaxies, quasars, and the appearance or disappearance of bodies. We witnessed firsthand the powerful destructive explosions of comet Shoemaker-Levy 9, which even broken-up was catastrophic¹⁵⁶. We witnessed those electro-comet explosions and have, since then, found many forms of evidence for catastrophe in space.

¹⁴¹ Based on potentially specious ice core samples... numerous studies have produced wildly different results.

¹⁴² <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-018-04322-x>

¹⁴³ Zamora et al.

¹⁴⁴ Note: the Earth is asymmetric in the core, and will have flipped just as shown in space demonstrations with wrenches <https://scitechdaily.com/is-earths-core-lopsided-something-strange-is-going-on-in-our-planets-interior/>

¹⁴⁵ Not to mention loads of cultural data, such as calendar names and the like. See: Velikovskism

¹⁴⁶ <https://www.scientificamerican.com/article/fresh-mammoth-carcass-from-siberia-holds-many-secrets/>

¹⁴⁷ <https://www.cnet.com/news/scientists-uncover-frozen-mammoth-blood-flows-out/>

¹⁴⁸ <http://www.talkorigins.org/faqs/mammoths.html>

¹⁴⁹ <https://www.theatlantic.com/science/archive/2019/12/permafrozen-dinner/604069/>

¹⁵⁰ "Worlds in Collision," Velikovsky, 1950

¹⁵¹ "Hopewell Octagons," Ibid., pp. 26-27 for diagrams showing overlays of mounds on top of scans of the north pole of Jupiter.

¹⁵² Hence Chinese reverence of the South.

¹⁵³ Using calipers for initial measurements we can get 3 and even 4 significant figures; with ratios units do not even matter.

¹⁵⁴ There's nothing to stop one from speculating, so long as angular momentum is conserved. It's perfectly reasonable.

¹⁵⁵ Comets fly by and break apart almost daily, so the system has changed, for sure. This is an unavoidable fact.

¹⁵⁶ Explosions usually larger than the Earth, though fragments were smaller than New York City

There is literally no data to suggest that the solar system has remained the same, this is merely Theology applied to Science, and it is incredibly wrong.

Figure 27 - Shoemaker Levy 9 impact vs. Earth scale¹⁵⁷

Enter the Micronova and Flares

One of the greatest examples of how we know it is not possible for the system to be the same all the time is the flares of the current star, our sun, which spews massive amounts of plasma material at high speeds¹⁵⁸. There is little reason to expect that this star would not have CME impacts with bodies in our solar system, and that these impacts would have no effect. Even the SM allows for light-pushing momentum effects, and so there is little reason to suspect that in a **dynamic** system that there would be even one iota of static effects.

Electromagnetism Hidden in Plain Sight

The Biefeld-Brown Effect has been known about for 100 years, and is well established¹⁵⁹. However, astronomers like to blame light (as a massless particle¹⁶⁰) for momentum shifts in Voyager satellites and talk about gold foil sails, etc. But the reality is that the sun is ejecting an unbelievable amount of charge in all directions. This means that the objects are gathering charge around the sun, and then the obvious electric and magnetic forces coming from the sun are then pushing and pulling upon them. Let's start with the obvious existence of the electric force. They have measured the solar wind's charge density and found that each individual grain is worth 4V.¹⁶¹ The generally macro effect is however seen in the acceleration of plasma away from the sun, even as the material gets further away from the sun's surface¹⁶². This is obvious, then, that these are not kinetic explosions, and they have measured the magnetism and found it insufficient to explain the acceleration observed ($F=ma$)¹⁶³. Therefore, the only remaining unaccounted for (and obvious) effect is the Electric Force (Lorentz Force).

Birkeland Currents Enable Sudden Change

Birkeland currents (or flux ropes) have been observed in space, and that includes between Jupiter and Io¹⁶⁴, and Saturn and Enceladus¹⁶⁵. Also connections from the sun to our magnetic field have been verified.¹⁶⁶ These tubes provide a means for masses of charges to "pump" in and arrive, even suddenly and unexpectedly,

¹⁵⁷ https://www.bibliotecapleyades.net/halebopp/truthabout_halebopp/truthabout_halebopp18.htm

¹⁵⁸ Up to 50% the speed of light!

¹⁵⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Biefeld%E2%80%93Brown_effect

¹⁶⁰ Light cannot be a particle; it is a circuit that has properties of a wave and can be modeled as a particle! This has been covered in other works, but it would violate thermodynamics to be an actual particle.

¹⁶¹ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1808.03389.pdf>

¹⁶² Proof there is an Electric Field... as the magnetic field has been shown to be incapable of producing this acceleration.

¹⁶³ Again gravity only attracts and magnetism is not capable, so there must be another force. It is not "dark energy," so this leaves only the electric force.

¹⁶⁴ <https://arxiv.org/ftp/astro-ph/papers/0209/0209070.pdf>

¹⁶⁵ <https://www.jpl.nasa.gov/news/news.php?feature=7186>

¹⁶⁶ https://science.nasa.gov/science-news/science-at-nasa/2008/30oct_ftes

from long distances. Why can they travel these distances? BC's only degrade by the square root of distance, which enables them to be hundreds of times more efficient at long distances than traditional Faraday EMF.¹⁶⁷

Suppose then that there was a different star, it could have been receiving electric modulation from the Local Chimney, the galaxy, or even the approaching sun which may have begun to spiral with the Earth. From there it isn't that hard to imagine what a changing "diode" star would necessarily change the behavior of the Earth¹⁶⁸. Skeptical? We have now seen "space hurricanes" in the Earth's atmosphere¹⁶⁹, and it is a fact that the atmosphere is electrically active and interactive with the solar wind.

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Figure 28 - Space Hurricanes, credit: sci-news.com

From there how hard is it to imagine that energy, and pressure, flowing down from concentrated and high energy gradients towards the small structures, trying to create equilibrium. For the smaller structures, such as electrically connected volcanoes¹⁷¹, and air and water currents, the effect would be profound and extreme, even sudden (by geological standards). This could and likely does involve magnetic field changes, and pole flips, or magnetic excursions¹⁷².

Speaking of volcanoes, there is a solid reason to expect that they are not all related to these extended ice age periods: magnitude of scale. While temporary small degree shifts in average worldwide temperatures have been seen and verified by ice core and geologic study, never have any such volcanoes been capable of producing a mechanism to alter the climate for thousands to millions of years, and not by such a degree. The order of scale of energy level is simply not enough, even for the largest volcano. But a lot of volcanoes, set off by some higher magnitude event, such as drastic electric environmental or gravity changes, etc. which could heat up or agitate the mantle, the crust, or the core of the Earth even, and change volcanic behavior for a time.

¹⁶⁷ <http://www.ptep-online.com/2015/PP-41-13.PDF>

¹⁶⁸ https://science.nasa.gov/science-news/science-at-nasa/1999/ast13dec99_1

¹⁶⁹ <https://eos.org/articles/a-space-hurricane-spotted-above-the-polar-cap>

¹⁷⁰ <https://theconversation.com/theres-always-the-sun-solar-forcing-and-climate-change-1878>

¹⁷¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Volcanic_lightning

¹⁷² <https://academic.oup.com/gji/article/137/1/F1/701015>

But you need a mechanism to explain that kind of change, and ultimately, without wiping out all life on the surface via nova or CME, the only energy level which can do this is the EMF, and this is because stars are electric, and not gravity-fusion controlled explosions. Stars are structured to interact with cosmic bodies, and they are capable of drastic and disastrous changes, at any time, and this would filter down to smaller structures and lower energy systems (as thermodynamics requires). What's most important to note is that only structured electromagnetism and a unified force, the PEM, will be capable of explaining structured changes. Gravity is ubiquitous and unchanging, and incapable of producing these effects. This is why they cannot explain fusion properly enough to replicate it with pressure, but can with plasma via use of the PEM force¹⁷³. Remember: in PEM theory gravity is downwind, or remnant of the PEM interaction, and caused by mere relative arrangement of matter, as charges arrange themselves naturally into relative "stasis."¹⁷⁴ Once a significant portion of charges are moving, gravity ceases to be any barrier, and therefore hardly a total explanation for what we see in space or on Earth.

Muspelheim & Jotunheim

The appearance, almost ubiquitous around the world, of a realm of Hell, later on in the story is very curious and telling. We have in the story from the Sumero-Babylonians that Nibiru approached the sun, seeking its warmth, and that Jupiter (as Enlil) beckoned it forth to be a son, and the wife planet Neptune, and to take his place as their child. But we see in the Enuma Elish that this invasion was sudden, and destructive:

"... the star, which shineth in the heavens.
May he hold the Beginning and the Future, may they pay homage unto him,
Saying, "He who forced his way through the midst of Tiamat without resting,
Let his name be Nibiru, 'the Seizer of the Midst'!
For the stars of heaven he upheld the paths,
He shepherded all the gods like sheep!
He conquered Tiamat, he troubled and ended her life,"
In the future of mankind, when the days grow old," ~Tablet 7

One of the sources of confusion here is not only that Nibiru has been misidentified with his "father" the planet Jupiter whom turned him from black into the color we see now, as it charged up, but that Tiamat has been identified not only as the Earth but a portion of the Earth, some type of material which surrounded the Earth (a type of ring? Various satellites?) and was able to be disrupted. This must have happened out past where the Asteroid Belt is now, else this would be identified as the Hammered Bracelet. It is the author's contention that Jupiter has never been closer to the sun than it is now, but Saturn and the rest were closer to Jupiter.

The most compelling reason that Hades/Muspelheim must be Uranus must be Nibiru, however is that the planet sits at a 105° tilt angle! This is singular in the solar system, and has no other explanation. As a gas giant even the "impact" catastrophe proposed in the mainstream of astronomy makes no sense. Only its invasion of the system from elsewhere, becoming a Nemesis of the delicately balanced three body system in a special arrangement or solution, could account for the facts.

How do we know that this new body is a Hell or an enemy? Even in the myths Odin defeats Surtur. What would defeating Surtur with the sword of Ragnarok entail? A massive plasma-charge transfer from Jupiter towards Uranus which then changed the entire system, and which created such a disaster as to be named as a devilish activity. Clearly this affected the Osiris/Set myth which became then confused (or

¹⁷³ <https://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2020/04/200428142408.htm>

¹⁷⁴ Example: crystal matrices where the charges zip around and yet remain locked in a crystalline lattice, a shared environment of electrical behavior.

misinterpreted by later kingdoms or archaeologists) and came to misunderstand that Jupiter was Set when Osiris/Saturn was ripped into pieces. But instead, we see that it was Uranus which stole Jupiter's parts, or sent them away (Mercury, the Moon, etc.) and in the 5kya vicinity not only destroyed this delicate balance or conjunction, but caused a chain of events that led to the Deluge or some other catastrophe, and from then on associating Jupiter with both Lord and tricky wizard as well as the Grim Reaper. But in the background a secret lurking power remained, Hades. Hades was the 4th child of Kronos, but his genesis is not clear. He was never Lord but ever associated with the Underworld also named Hades. So we can see that this interaction was probably short, and once Jupiters' charge-stamp was upon Uranus, the sun had a specific place to put him, where he remains in magnetic phase lock to this day. It is not the same monster as Rama encounters in the Ramayana, because Uranus is not blue nor has no "eye" to speak of. But Poseidon was always a peer to Zeus, and without a stamp of Jupiter's charge via thunderbolt (or sword of Odin), it has remained free to traverse on its own wide orbit, in its own interaction with the Sun. But Uranus was a mightier lord, yet only to rule in Hell. Therefore we can understand that Odin defeats Surtur, but not forever. And when the sword is pulled again Ragnarok will begin, as Surtur will reappear. Very ominous ideas, which remain to this day as paranoia about a Planet X or Planet 9 linger on. Nemesis, indeed!

Did it, however, increase the planet Earth's temperature? Or decrease it? That would be an implication from the approach to the midst of Tiamat... but is there clear evidence? Let's take a look at the period (and the author is literally doing this for the first time as this is being written) from the 7kya to 4kya, when the hypothesis purports that Hades would appear. And let's also compare with a site like Sardinia for age. According to literature, Li Muri dates from the 5th Millenium BC¹⁷⁵ and the following diagram shows temperatures:

Figure 29: holocene temps; Credit: RealClimate¹⁷⁶

¹⁷⁵ <https://canvas.gu.se/courses/25523/files/977417/download?wrap=1>

¹⁷⁶ <https://www.realclimate.org/index.php/archives/2013/09/paleoclimate-the-end-of-the-holocene/>

What do we find? There is a spike as expected at the Jupiter boundary 7kya, but more importantly the “Jotunheim” dip after with the “ice giants” is followed by a sudden and precipitous spike at the 6kya boundary, as postulated in EPEMC hypothesis! This was not a factor in determining the timeline but it certainly is another line of evidence to support it. That’s the power of this cosmology. Moreover, as the Earth is moved away from Jupiter there is a corresponding fall in temperatures as the Earth’s climate becomes dominated by the “Habitable Zone’s” voltage and current properties, rather than the old star’s. In point of fact, temperatures dip enough for ice to grow on Greenland and Antarctica erasing land where flora once existed and sailors once knew they could land! It’s important to note the planet would have flipped around this time as it moved from one voltage environment to another, and the solar wind would dominate interaction with Earth’s poles, not Jupiter’s massive sun-sized magnetosphere! Based on temperature change we can basically pinpoint this turning over into the Biblical era about 3kya, and shortly before the Exodus events involving Venus. Please note that Moses’ trouble getting the Hebrews to worship the correct Lord (he was Egyptian trained, after all and had access to ancient knowledge) would stem from the fact that by 2700YBP by Velikovsky’s reckoning, Jupiter would be a tiny dot, whilst Venus was a great big green raging comet monster that looked like a cow (or bull). This bull motif was a replacement of the original Shamash Bull seen at Gobekli Tepe, and so it is clear why some cultures would begin to venerate cows and not stop, even for thousands of years In Karnak they slaughtered them and made massive sarcophagi for them. But that is another story for another time.

And where did Jotunheim go? It is almost certainly planet Neptune, and almost certainly it faded away as we moved towards Odin/Asgard and Jupiter, as Neptune is indeed very far away. The memory of ice ages were only recalled later as temperatures dropped again. But the powerful story of cold origins does indeed pale in comparison to the fiery battle between Odin and the dreaded devilish monster Surtur!

For those who want to speak about greenhouse gases at the time, the author will reassure you there is no correlation. As they rise, temperatures actually have fallen over thousands of years:

Figure 30 : Holocene Greenhouse Gases; credit: Climate Etc.¹⁷⁷

¹⁷⁷ <https://judithcurry.com/2017/04/30/nature-unbound-iii-holocene-climate-variability-part-a/>

Part 4 - Orbital Revisioning

Unfortunately for the public, the best computer models to play around with only have gravitic forces in the game (Universal Sandbox 2), but as discussed the PEM cannot be neglected in the least. Electro-static tidal lock, magnetic phase lock, and the pressures of plasma winds and the Biefeld-Brown Effect are simply too difficult to model. Instead the author must make rough hand drawn diagrams to propose possible orientations. What follows therefore are not scientific assertions but a series of hypotheses based upon evidence and predictive, perhaps even intuitive modeling. Bear in mind, however, we may never rightly know if any of it is 100% true, as records have been unfortunately destroyed, or not written but carved and drawn, misinterpreted, etc. Only by carefully plotting together all the cultural evidence and motifs, and applying some rationalism, removing pseudoscientific ideas like aliens or Dark Matter, will we be able to find a reasonable timeline plus hypothesis for a workable cosmology that can cover most, if not all of the facts.

The Watcher Moon

The author saw a funny meme today, and it goes as follows:

The most ironic, and to the author, hilarious thing about this meme is that the Earth's moon is adopted *from Jupiter*. Or rather, according to the epic myths, the moon was sent, as a watcher over us, or rather, over Tiamat.

Figure 31 - Some humor; credit: Safely Endangered

As mentioned before, Tiamat was both a region of the sky apparently watery in view and maybe loaded with actual water (from Saturn initially?), and the Earth itself. Or, perhaps the interpretation as Earth has been mixed up with the death of an unknown body. But if so, there's no evidence of major sources of water, or dead plant life, in the asteroid belt now. So it seems that the skull being split in two, is a reference not to Earth but a previous moon or other body, but that the "lifeless body" was instead the death over Earth. The installation of a Watcher over the "dead body" of the Earth is clearly reference to Marduk (Jupiter's) own Jovian like body of the moon¹⁷⁸, which as before mentioned resembles other Galilean moons rather than Saturnian ones (which tend to have water and atmospheres).

In this section we will examine not just the electrical scarring evidence from the previous Appendix B of the other paper (the M plates¹⁷⁹), but other signs that the Moon is nothing like the Earth, and in fact constitutes

¹⁷⁸ Comparing macro structure and not necessarily composition (as of yet).

¹⁷⁹ Ibid., pp.159-176

an invasive body, which has a strong electrical attraction (though waning as charges siphon off in our outer plasmasphere). This moon, of course, has terrified, comforted, and even led people spiritually astray for thousands of years. But it most definitely did not come from a Big Whack, which can never work, because of momentum considerations.¹⁸⁰

Figure 32 - Common Depiction of the Big Whack Theory; Credit: Astrobites/M. Zevin

Neptune and the Three-Body Problem

Moving from the near to the very far, we encounter the strangeness of the planet Neptune. It is dazzling in hue, and has a rich history within human myth, and yet is too far away to be realistically considered important in the pantheon, from humanity's modern perspective. Seriously, it is so pale and blue, even at its brightest almost nobody can find it in a backdrop of brighter stars¹⁸¹. Yet, it is an enigma which has fascinated mankind for a long time. In this part we will explore the tantalizing evidence that Neptune was first grown and became part of a triad, which then moved in a triquetra, and then became part of a "war" that separated the arranged tree, and divided the lineage of the gods.

Looking at the evidence from the "Nazca Meme Cat" to Tables 3 & 4, we notice that continuously there is the presence of a third gas giant player. We also see this in the Chinese plasmascripts and plasmaglyphics. Usually, it is true, one or two "maltese cross" motifs appear, just as we see two at Cahokia or in Egypt. But also we find, on occasion, that a third does appear, and more importantly we see this at Bakoni, Maputo, Sardinia,

¹⁸⁰ After a time the smaller object would need to rotate faster than the larger, to conserve momentum, and as the distance changes, and chaotically, it would (in a purely kinetic system) change the rotation momentum. But in fact, electrostatic forces keep things as they are. Anything else violates the laws of thermodynamics and Newton's Laws of Motion.

¹⁸¹ "Neptune is the only planet in our solar system not visible to the naked eye." Which begs the question why Poseidon was so well worshiped worldwide. <https://solarsystem.nasa.gov/planets/neptune/in-depth/>

and other “oldest places” on Earth. We see them near to or associated with the Cosmic Egg with attendant features discussed above and in Table 3. Why? It is the author’s conjecture that this represents a short period of measurable time which could not be otherwise well recorded because Neptune came out flaring. Very soon, radiation and weather conditions probably led to a decline in population health and numbers, and people were forced underground. It may be that they drew rock art underground about the monster god, there are horrific plasmascripts in the Chinese, particularly the one for “mask” and these themes were repeated in the Mars/Venus cataclysmic era in the Late Archaic to Transition Periods. But Neptune’s emergence was far too early, and besides, the alignment of these would have broken down fairly “fast” (by cosmological standards). Yet not so fast that there wasn’t a clear period of time when the god of the Sea ruled the skies with his trident, and yet was not Zeus/Enlil nor Kronos/Enki. When we look at the ratios in Table 2 and 5, we see that while Uranus almost never conforms to the ratio modes, which have definite resonances, Neptune does in several places, all too well. Unfortunately, its DR is all too similar to rocky bodies, and the sun, and this makes it nearly impossible to prove... except... that the Nazca Meme Cat clearly shows the emergence of a gaseous body, which is smaller, from the Cosmic Egg. Combining this with the Ramayana data, we see that the conjecture is not likely far from reality. Poseidon and Shiva were lords, for a brief time. But how, when, etc. is not clear. The author thinks the answers will come from the new Tepe excavations over the next 10-20 years.

Jovian Octagons and Early Religion

In a very detailed previous paper, the author set forth the mathematical certitude and facts surrounding the Hopewell/Allegewi mounds of the Ohio River valley and their astronomical observations of the north pole of Jupiter. This proved 3 things:

1. The Hopewell definitely had trigonometry and probably writing, and did not need a telescope (and there is no evidence of said telescope)
2. The northern hemisphere of Earth was facing to where it could see the north pole of Jupiter, in enough direct line of sight to create asymmetric octagon mounds that leave a distinct pattern which has no equivalent on Earth, at 3 separate locations no less.
3. The Earth obviously orbited close enough to Jupiter to make this observation.

This last point is bolstered by the previous work the author had done showing the Ramesses II Stele had accuracy of DR measurements for Jupiter and Saturn to within 5% of satellite measurements.¹⁸² The image used may be less precise than the actual stele (and almost certainly is), but was measured with calipers to make sure to get a 3 orders of precise magnitude levels... Enough to prove within a very strong certitude, statistically speaking that there is direct observation of Saturn and Jupiter made by the dynastic Egyptians. At this time, Jupiter and Saturn were no longer huddled close together, and again there is no evidence the Egyptians had telescopes, even if they had high precision engineering, machining, and maybe even electric field generation¹⁸³!

So what was the point of these octagon mounds? What was the point, for that matter, of conical mounds? The author is postulating here not simply that there is a plethora of cosmic hill/mountain motifs around the world, and that this happened as a result of the two hills becoming one Great Mountain in the 7kya boundary. That’d be too easy. Anyone can see that. The author is instead proposing that the motif was repeated, between the 7kya and 1400 AD period no less than three times, causing radical re-adoption of religious themes. First the Creator-Father, dropping the feminine, and His weapons of war. Then the Warrior Son. Then the Warrior daughter turned traitor. Then the messiah star which was alternately Mars or Venus depending on the culture. Finally by the era of the Aztecs and Cahokians, the Death God, which was almost

¹⁸² “Ramses Stele” paper, Ibid., pp. 3-5

¹⁸³ “Magnetic Universe Theory” paper, Ibid., pp. 6-7

always Venus, and the mounds had deterred from the original step pyramid shape of the early days to simple platforms or large pyramids with platforms.

The relation between the obloid spherical shape of the star, and the octagons is not altogether clear unless the octagon represents the “crown” of the Lord. At the Garden of the Gods in Illinois, there is not only an astrobleme, but subsequent nearby liesegang banding with direct electrical evidence. At the top of this site is a large asymmetric octagon which still requires some measurement. Directly underneath the octagon section is a previous hexagon section. Is this a motif, or coincidence? At any rate, the most distinct impression of a platform altar is presented which was chiseled to represent one of the gods, or both.

Meanwhile in Kentucky there is an entire hilltop with the above portion removed, revealing the stone platform layer below. It is made in the shape of the cosmic egg at a ratio currently over 1.4 but originally probably 1.25 or less¹⁸⁴. There is no direct evidence of habitation, and the layer is definitely natural. So the removal would have required some many thousands of hours of manpower. What was done there to worship Shamash is not known and probably never can be known because of contamination/destruction on the property due to logging.

But there is some connection between the early Saturnian and the later Jovian into the Messianic. We see this most readily at the conical mound culture of the Khumry/Cymru and Celts of the British Isles, who shared such a commonality of mound religion with the Allegewi/Hopewell that they merged and formed the Ft. Ancient in the 1100-1400 AD era in Kentucky and Ohio/Indiana region (until destroyed by rival Ameroindians and maybe Chinese aided Cahokians? In the 1400s).

Why do we see the ancient druidic turned Christian tradition involved with mounds at all? From other work by the author there is evidence of Yellow Hill (Caer Melyn, lit: brown fort, aka Camelot) in Cardiff, and hexagon “ring fort” (as per the theories of other researchers), all throughout south Wales¹⁸⁵. Given the common use of 14 or 7 pointed crowns in the isles¹⁸⁶, and the belief in worship (which apparently the Cherokee did not share in common with the Nicotani/Ft. Ancient, whom they destroyed¹⁸⁷), it is clear that the worship of the Great Man (Zeus/Jupiter) was a common belief during the Stonehenge days¹⁸⁸.

Figure 33 - Royal Crown of Richard III;
credit: Andy Rain/EPA

Henges are another commonality between the allegewi and druidic worshippers¹⁸⁹. But what is unique about EPEMC prediction is that we **expect** the 56 post holes¹⁹⁰, wooden holes, stones, etc. in rough

¹⁸⁴ Due to acceleration downhill by stones under erosion.

https://www.academia.edu/37817203/Trip_Report_Culvertown_Platform_Formation for photos.

¹⁸⁵

https://www.academia.edu/38993303/Caer_Melyn_Camelot_Cosmic_Hillfort_of_the_King_The_Yellow_Hill_fort_as_a_Cosmic_Hill_or_mountain_motif_and_symbol_of_a_Kings_authority

¹⁸⁶ <https://www.theguardian.com/science/2019/dec/28/richard-iii-and-a-roman-rabbit-the-finds-of-the-decade>

¹⁸⁷ “Myths of the Cherokee,” J. Mooney, 1897 <https://www.sacred-texts.com/nam/cher/motc/index.htm>

¹⁸⁸ Roughly 4kya+

¹⁸⁹ https://www.academia.edu/37490311/Plasma_Petroglyphs_Plasmaglyphs_Earthworks_and_the_Megafauna_Extinction
pp. 13-15

¹⁹⁰ As per Dr. Anthony Peratt

<https://plasmauniverse.info/downloads-petros/Peratt&YaoAurora-PrehistoryPhys-Scr-T131.2008c.pdf>

octagon to circular form, found at Stonehenge¹⁹¹, and nearby (and even older) sites. These conform to the Perattian Thunderbolt hypothesis, which of course, has a “smoking gun” in the center of Kithiki (Kentucky) at the “Big Sink” “astrobleme” which is neither a sink nor astrobleme, as has been shown in detail via LiDAR analysis¹⁹².

So what does it mean? It means first and foremost most mound sites are under-dated, likely because they are heaped Earth of restored religions¹⁹³. Christianity had revivals, and so did North American tribes and probably in Peru etc. Why have multiple periods of Mayans, or “nazca lines” or pyramid eras in Africa... if there were no precipitating reason nor gods to please? It is likely that after catastrophes there would be a strong revival of fear of the Lord. After the 1348 AD and subsequent Black Plagues, which probably had catastrophic origins, was there not also a subsequent Renaissance?! The evidence for these plagues being related to a comet or other event are strong. So is that of the Justinian plague, Spanish Flu, and more recently the author detailed the COVID initial epidemic and its relation to comet Atlas C4¹⁹⁴!

What else can be known about early religions and the changing orbits?

Leaving behind the safe shores of educated speculation, we must enter the world of pure but logical speculation, to talk about what religious life may have been like. There is a disconnect in current anthropology, and a great many gaps named “everything is a tomb” or “death cult.” That disconnect is the idea that people back in the old days were quaint, unsophisticated, and really a bit naive about the world. But when we look for evidence what we typically find is the opposite¹⁹⁵. Sophisticated and wise sexual practices and protocols, advanced codes of ethics that didn’t require cumbersome codes of law that generate controversies, a true wit that came down to strict philosophy (not too erudite) that dealt with reality, and human problems.

Such an example of this is at the Cahokia visitor center in Illinois. Display after display of people in loincloths and bare-chested women. Of course this is pure rubbish since the winters of the midwest are notoriously brutal. When you come to the end of the displays there are photographs of the plains Indians in black and white. They are all wearing the most elaborate and beautiful clothing. Plains Indians were highly ritualized and sophisticated. So we should suppose that a civilized culture like the Cahokians, with stockade walls, armies, row agriculture of maize, and who were able to receive the Chinese delegations in the 1430s or 1440s would be ... naked savages? This kind of anthropological disconnect is all too reminiscent of the accidental racism fostered by the overt racism of early Victorian era archeology and Egyptology, which became the “innocent” grave robbing of American archeology in the 1880s through the 1960s in America. Such a thing keeps us from listening to the myths and tales of the historic tribes which tell us quite plainly what they did and did not do and believe. Usually that means our sciences are highly inaccurate.

There’s another obsessive way we project into the past: pottery. Unless the pottery specifically has images on it, there isn’t much more pottery can tell you about a culture than your tupperware can about our entire society. Sure it can tell you that we have a plastic society. But it cannot describe the plastic of the keyboard, or the digital era, or the sophisticated interconnectivity of social media and subcultures of murky places on the Internet!

¹⁹¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Aubrey_holes

¹⁹² “Addendum 1” paper,

https://www.academia.edu/39006416/Proposed_Discovery_of_Perattian_Thunderbolt_of_the_Gods_Strike_Location_in_Versailles_KY_Comparison_of_Predicted_Models_and_LiDAR_scans_of_Big_Sink_location_in_Woodford_County_Addendum_for_Plasmaglyphs_and_the_Megafauna_Extinction

¹⁹³ Unfortunately, because of erosion, you’d never be able to date the older material, only the newest. Or get wildly conflicting dates, as they did at Great Serpent mound, which is older and yet younger than supposed.

¹⁹⁴

https://www.academia.edu/43190878/OPINION_On_Gurus_Electric_Universe_Predictions_Bio_electrics_Comet_5G_and_Futurism pp. 3

¹⁹⁵ “Megafauna Extinction...” Paper 1, Ibid., Part 1

In this way, we can see that making suppositions about the unsophisticated hunter-gatherer tribes based on the pottery they use or “nutting holes” (which are not for nuts), etc. is preposterous to the extreme, and full of hubris.

Instead, we might start with what they show they cared about.

In wall after wall in America we have graffiti. It contains gang signs, art, pornography, curse or swear words, hobo signs, etc. Many of these hobo signs actually have ancient plasmaglyphics in them, as it happens. But the point is we see signs of disease in the culture.

Figure 35 - Hobo graffiti (meaning unknown), with tri-god spheres, double arm/peak, and cosmic eye motifs; credit: author (taken in Louisville, KY)

But in native and celtic and other aboriginal rock art we do not find nude women, or signs of bloody torture, or cursing God or each other. We find either depictions of Nature or of the sky. And more typically: the sky. It is clear the Ameroindians revered these sites, for even in the 1800s, Chief Red Bird of the Cherokee imperiled his life to guard the Manchester “Red Bird” Petroglyphs of his cave and the nearby rock, and died for it, because the Cherokee had moved far south¹⁹⁶. But he was a guardian only. Now the site is imperiled as it has no guardian. But the point is that the Ameroindians guarded it because it spoke to the same religion which touched their own spirit-based animism, centered around a Great Creator. Whoever made the carvings, the Nicotani or Allegewi or otherwise, they shared a similar basis for religiosity.

Yet, perhaps not enough.

So is it that there were many outgrowths of the Saturnian religions which became many types of worship? Isn't it a bit ironic that the Spanish sought (rightfully) to end the human sacrifice to Mars (or Venus), when they themselves practiced knightly warfare, which began its origins in worship to Ares, the god of War, or perhaps even Athena, goddess of war, if one goes all the way back through Rome to the Greeks? Certainly they did so for Christ's sake, and for conquest. However, the Christus prophecy¹⁹⁷ originated on account of a heracleian messiah motif or archetype, from its inception. What was meant by such a messiah was a Horus-like hero who would sweep the sky and Earth clean of evil, and restore God (lit: the High Tower¹⁹⁸) to the Pillar of Creation. It is almost certainly true that this is what the Aztecs and Mixtecs and Mayans believed, as well. It is also what the Cahokians believed, as far as a Cosmic Pole being central to understanding the Sun god.¹⁹⁹

¹⁹⁶ Literally to the Smokies of North Carolina, see: Dr. Tankersley's work

¹⁹⁷ <https://www.gotquestions.org/Serapis-Christus.html>

¹⁹⁸ Psalm 18:2

¹⁹⁹ Paper 1, Ibid, Figure 15

Where did all the Pyramids go?

Mankind loved making step and platform pyramids²⁰⁰. Later, as described conical mounds were considered just as sufficient. But when it came to war and sacrifice, or combat (such as Sumo, an early Shinto tradition in agricultural Japan), one needed a flat single or double tiered platform pyramid²⁰¹.

Figure 36 - Cahokia (background) with 56 post hole henge (foreground); credit: U. of Chicago Press

And then as suddenly as that was a thing, it too ended. The precise reasons for switching between steps and tall pointy pyramids or cones and then to platforms is a bit of a mystery. There are early platforms as well²⁰². Along the Green and Tennessee Rivers in Kithiki there is a plethora of oversized platforms formed from “shell middens”. But as mentioned above, they were also for the technology of making dark earths²⁰³, possibly. But they are generally flat, and all older than 2500 YBP. That is not, to the author’s knowledge, common.

This tradition probably *returned* on account of some change in the solar system which reminded mankind of the tales of the early days. If we look, the majority of step/platforms were made either pre 2500 YBP, or in the middle ages of the AD period. Similarly, while Mars’ approach to the Earth was 2700 YBP (circa), the Kofuns were not made until the 300 AD+ and mostly middle ages²⁰⁴. What gives? If Mars had reapproached, then surely there would be writings about it. It may be a matter of cultural co-emergence (ie, revivalism), but the author suspects that again comets and plagues served then (as now with eclipses) to fascinate and increase religious fervor among the masses. Consider the Middle Ages dual phenomenon of towers in Tibet, and in Italy²⁰⁵. Was this something re-seen, or a reminder from some comet of a previous religious belief system? Considering the connections of the dark ages to a comet causing pestilence²⁰⁶, the author favors the latter.

So why did the pyramids (and other megaliths) go away for a time: war, pestilence, famine, and the lack of gods (planetoids) to look at? If they are just dots, no one cares even still, except astronomers of course. We use telescopes to make them relevant again. Otherwise, they wouldn’t be. They weren’t before Galileo, save perhaps for sailors/captains and magick practitioners like astrologers.

²⁰⁰ Again: see Cahokia (or as the Chinese called it “Feng-Tu”)

²⁰¹ “Sumo” paper, Ibid. ; Note that many Mississippian mounds were also double-tiered, while many were single tiered... even at the same site, such as Moundville, AL.

²⁰² Such as Poverty Point

²⁰³ “Amazon Connections” paper, Ibid., pp. 3-4

²⁰⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kofun_period ; note the overlap here with the end of “Adena” and start of “Hopewell” period. Probably not a coincidence.

²⁰⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Himalayan_Towers compare to those of Bologna, Italy, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Towers_of_Bologna ; both are 12th-13th Century.

²⁰⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lvOHBjkBpyM> ; again compare to the author’s paper on COVID.

Language and Writing

There is probably no single greater example of the power of the gods (save perhaps war) in influence to mankind than the creation of written plasmaglyphic and plasmascriptic languages. Sanskrit, Chinese, Coelbren, Hebrew, Rongorongo, Arabian... these all contain symbology of the early gods and correspondences to rock art. It is obvious that the power of spoken word was some means of communicating not only with the gods, but to borrow their power and communicate it with each other. We see no better example of the hidden truth of this (and the megalithic building mystery) than in the Tower of Babylon story.

“11 And the whole earth was of one language, and of one speech.

2 And it came to pass, as they journeyed from the east, that they found a plain in the land of Shinar; and they dwelt there.

3 And they said one to another, Go to, let us make brick, and burn them thoroughly. And they had brick for stone, and slime had they for mortar.

4 And they said, Go to, let us build us a city and a tower, whose top may reach unto heaven; and let us make us a name, lest we be scattered abroad upon the face of the whole earth.

5 And the Lord came down to see the city and the tower, which the children of men builded.

*6 And the Lord said, Behold, the people is one, and **they have all one language**; and this they begin to do: and **now nothing will be restrained from them**, which they have imagined to do.*

7 Go to, let us go down, and there confound their language, that they may not understand one another's speech.

8 So the Lord scattered them abroad from thence upon the face of all the earth: and they left off to build the city.

9 Therefore is the name of it called Babel; because the Lord did there confound the language of all the earth: and from thence did the Lord scatter them abroad upon the face of all the earth.” ~King James Version (emphasis added)

The first, and most curious line of this is the idea that people were of one language, of one “speech.” This is unlikely given what we know of Mesopotamia, let alone everywhere else. Therefore it is taken by the author to mean that there was a way of expressing to one another within their known world, that everyone knew what things meant. This is our first evidence of plasmaglyphics, or perhaps math. Next we see in the 4th verse that there is direct reference to a city in the sky and the Heavenly pillar motif. Usually in art this is rendered in a step pyramid or step cylindrical fashion.

Next most curious is that the Lord *went down*, and said “Let **us** go down.” The plurality of Elohim and the lordship of El/Yahweh has long been a topic in theology and sinology. But in EPEMC it is simplified. The Lord here, based on the time, would be Jupiter/Jehovah, and the “us” is the pantheon of moons surrounding Jupiter, which in this case replicates the original Saturn/Elohim formation, almost too much to be ignored. After the “arrival” of Jove, or Ba'al, it would have been an era of megalithic building, and after departure, the abrupt end of it, as electro-gravitic conditions changed. And lo: we find abrupt megalithic cessation at Baalbek, Dendera, and China, and almost a total end to the making of dolmens worldwide, in the late Archaic and early Megalithic Period (~6000-7000 YBP)²⁰⁷.

After the fall or collapse of such great megalithic civilizations, is there any surprise that the people would then scatter? Not at all. After the fall of old Egypt and the old gods, and the Hebrews fled, and the deserts consumed the plains... why would pyramid building of the grand form continue and how would it continue? It is therefore a basic presumption that if even in Egypt and China where the love of pyramid building was so complete and in Egypt even a science... if the pyramids become smaller, weaker, made with lesser

²⁰⁷ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dolmen>

stones, that something major had shifted, and around the world indeed it spelled the end of pyramid building. Except, perhaps, in Mexico with the Mayans, and only because after the first era died away something or some force instigated a revival of Mayanism and the ancient religions of the Olmec. The Olmec heads, with their round (obviously spheroid basis) giant god heads, left an indelible impression upon Central America as to what the correct worship of the gods was: megalithic, and bloody.

As for language, it is beyond the scope of the author and his expertise to say much about the influence the plasmaglyphics could have had with common speech²⁰⁸, or differentiation. However, it is certain to say that as speech naturally evolves, and so did the pantheons because of the changing solar system conditions²⁰⁹, that the words and thoughts of the ancient people were incredibly foreign to our own, and yet as sophisticated, for they were biologically modern people²¹⁰. If so much can change from era to era, what does this say about our own “live as bright and as brief as a lightning bug” society? Probably that we will be as inscrutable, if we are known at all, to future archaeologists, as the ancients are to ours presently²¹¹. Mankind will hopelessly filter ideas of the past through modern (and inappropriate) lenses, trying to project barbarism upon the past in order to support the weak idea that modernity is inherently more civilized and has nothing to learn²¹².

But the cost of this is clear: an ignorance of what has happened to us has led to mass hysteria²¹³, confusion, and a level of species’ self-destruction (and of nature) that is dangerously Babel-like.

Conclusions

The initial paper’s hypothesis remains intact. The mechanism has shifted due to new and better information. While the original was capable of predicting the doom of the Michigan ice impact hypothesis (almost DOA, as it were), the paper failed in identifying the source of the electrical power as coming from the Moon. Now it is understood that the Moon’s arrival and interaction was a middle event in the Megalithic or late Archaic Period. But the death of Shamash, our first star, provides both ample substance and energy, for our needs for 6k+ giant Perattian thunderbolts (vajra), which then in turn provide the needed vector for all the changes of the Younger Dryas, and the strange selective extinctions thereof. It is supported by physical evidence and native testimony²¹⁴, mound and megalithic structure, rock art and human record with mathematical soundness.

The real question is: where do we go from here? If Neptune²¹⁵ and then Uranus have flared²¹⁶, and if all the planets and moons with atmospheres are experiencing climate change right now... is this a continuation of the events described, or something new caused by natural solar motion through the Milky Way^{217 218}? Magnetic excursions and pole flips are a part of Earthen existence. Will our fragile society survive these? Looking into the past, what we see is that from Period to Period mankind *is* resilient and makes adjustments both socially and religiously, in order to explain the events. With modern science we *may* be more capable of making

²⁰⁸ Perhaps the reader can attend to a great YouTube channel like NativLang and find these answers.

<https://www.youtube.com/user/NativLang>

²⁰⁹ As described in this paper and others’ works, like Jno Cook and Julian West, Dwardu Cardona, Dave Talbott, etc.

²¹⁰ 40kya-60kya https://www2.palomar.edu/anthro/homo2/mod_homo_4.htm

²¹¹ <https://www.bbc.com/future/article/20151127-how-will-future-archaeologists-study-us>

²¹² Take our poor forest management techniques, as compared to Native techniques such as controlled burning! Yellowstone itself was a managed environment, and it is looking like the Amazon was as well.

²¹³ Velikovsky called it “mankind in amnesia” long before Graham Hancock; the author’s paper on End of the World Media gives frightening statistics on the costs of the Us nuclear program, in real dollars and in terms of buying food:

https://www.academia.edu/36753646/Investments_in_Ragnarok_Comparisons_and_Conclusions_from_the_study_of_Media_Business_and_Government_investments_in_End_of_the_World_myth_story_and_preparation

²¹⁴ Paper 1, Ibid., Part 1 and Appendix B, S Plates

²¹⁵ <https://www.nasa.gov/feature/goddard/2020/dark-storm-on-neptune-reverses-direction-possibly-shedding-a-fragment>

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²¹⁷ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hilN8eNp930&list=PLHSoxioQtwZcm9KdHf_n8WsF2IFB4FVvg

²¹⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=V2decDcEJqo&list=PLHSoxioQtwZcVcFC85TxEEiirgFXwhfsw>

adjustments, if we are willing to consider needs and evidence. That will possibly be tested in the coming decades. But what is sure is that the words of the ancients cry out to us, warning us to listen, and challenging our preconceptions and misconceptions about cosmogony. We must use a cosmology like PEMC to make smart, correct, accurate, and *wise* predictions, if we are to survive and be remembered, hopefully as well or even better (it seems) than the first Egyptians, Sumerians, Atlanteans (perhaps?), and Allegewi; and all the cultures we've never heard of for they flourished and vanished ere we could discover them or their secrets! We have better learn, or we may be the next Paracans.

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